

Intention to Use Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying

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ABSTRACT: This research was conducted to examine the intention to use an induction electric stove according to the theory of trying. The variables involved in the analysis are traits, theory of trying, the attitude of adopting an induction electric cooker (AM) and the desire to adopt an induction electric cooker (IM). Traits are general self-confidence (GSC) and cynicism (Cyn). Theory trying is attitude towards success (AS), attitude towards failure (AF), attitude towards learning (IA).

Respondents are 197 of the respondents in Indonesia. Respondents who deserved to be processed were 124. The questionnaire used Google form media. The analysis technique used is PLS SEM with the help of WarpPLS 7.0 software.

The results obtained are Attitude towards success has a significant positive effect on the attitude of adopting an induction electric stove. Attitude towards failure has no negative and insignificant effect on attitude towards induction cooker adoption. Attitudes toward learning to use an induction cooker have a significant positive effect on attitudes towards the adoption of an induction cooker. Attitudes towards the adoption of induction hobs have a positive impact on the intention to adopt induction hobs. Confidence in general has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards success. Self-confidence in general has a significant negative effect on attitudes towards failure. Confidence in general has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove. Cynicism has a significant negative effect on attitudes towards success. Cynicism has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards failure. Cynicism has a significant positive effect on attitudes toward learning to use an induction hob. There is a pattern that is different from previous research related to conversion plans, namely the obligation of the state and government support, both equipment and direct cash assistance related to the conversion program.

KEYWORDS: general self-confidence, cynicism, attitude towards adoption, adoption intention, attitude towards success, attitude towards failure, attitude towards learning

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Ratification of Law No. 16 of 2017 concerning ratification of the Paris Agreement To The United Nations Framework Convention On Climate Change (Paris Agreement On The United Nations Framework Convention On Climate Change) on October 24, 2016 shows the commitment of the Indonesian government together with other countries in the world to maintain global temperature rise below 2oC and in an effort to limit global temperature rise to 1.5oC above pre-industrial levels. The Government of Indonesia in 2030 has made a commitment to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 834 million tons of CO₂ or 29% of the conditions of Business as Usual (BaU). Emission sources include emissions from fuel combustion in various sectors and fugitive emissions. The sectoral approach to emissions is calculated according to the activity sector, such as energy production (electricity),(ESDM Energy and Mineral Resources Data and Information Center, 2020).

An atmosphere containing high levels of CO₂ results in various health problems, such as inflammation, altered bone composition, kidney disorders, respiratory acidosis, altered behavior and physiology, and oxidative stress.(Jacobson et al., 2019). Infants and children are especially vulnerable to increased CO₂ in the atmosphere because they take in more air than they weigh to grow and develop(Faustmann et al., 2000). Rapidly increasing CO₂ can replace oxygen in the atmosphere so that it can cause rather severe hypoxemia and result in things that are not good for health(Beheshti et al., 2018).

BPS data for 2021 obtained information that in the period 2015 – 2019, there was an increase in the use of energy products from year to year by households. Households use 1,365 PJ of energy products in 2015. Meanwhile, their use in 2019 is

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1,550 PJ. Figure 1.1 shows data that in the period 2015 – 2019 households used their main energy product from oil, namely gasoline for their personal transportation needs. In addition, the use of other energy products by households is electricity, LPG, and biofuels.

Figure 1.1 Distribution of Use of Household Energy Products (PJ) 2015-2019

The Indonesian government continues to encourage the use of induction electric stoves for clean energy use. The switch from using LPG fuel to an induction electric stove for cooking was able to save gas subsidies worth Rp. 4.8 trillion in 5 years according to information from the Secretary General of the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, Ego Syahril. The target of the government's efforts in diverting the use of LPG fuel to induction electric stoves is 71.7 million household customers PT PLN (Persero)(Spaceenergi.com, 2020). Moreover, at the COP26 meeting in Glasgow, England on 1 – 12 November 2021, where the Indonesian government's commitment is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 29% (by the Indonesian government) and 41% (with international support) in 2030(Indicators, 2021).

An induction electric stove is a stove that allows a person to cook without using a burning fire, but electrical energy which is a source of heat energy. Apart from being said to be more economical and safe, induction electric stoves are also easier to clean. An induction electric stove is a stove that uses electrical energy as heat energy. The induction electric stove works when the cooking utensil is placed on the stove, then an alternating electric current is passed from inside the stove body through a coil of wire. Then, the heat generated is directly channeled into the cooking utensil so that when it comes into contact with the limbs, it does not feel hot and is relatively safe.

The induction electric stove has a higher level of efficiency compared to the gas stove, because the induction electric stove induces magnetic flux to the stainless steel pot or pan used for cooking. The mechanism of the induction electric stove induces magnetic flux to the bottom of the pot so that eddy currents occur, because a stainless steel pot or pan has a large resistance it will generate heat. This does not produce heat that goes out into the environment like a gas stove that gives off heat to the environment. Therefore induction electric stoves are more environmentally friendly(Hasanah & Handayani, 2016).

The induction electric stove has a working principle like Figure 1.2, namely when cooking utensils made of stainless steel are placed on the stove, wherein the induction electric stove contains coils/coils which are energized by alternating current electricity (AC) so as to produce an oscillating magnetic field and generate eddy currents through the resistance of stainless steel cookware and make it hot so that it can be used for cooking. This heat is less spread to the surrounding environment.

Figure 1.2 The Working Principle of an Induction Electric Stove

Source : <https://yaletools.com/id/all-kinds-of-stoves/>

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Research on induction cookers is mostly about the technical specifications or the technical side compared to the marketing side, such as; Comparison of energy efficiency and cost of induction electric stoves against electric stoves and gas stoves (Hasanah & Handayani, 2016), Performance Test of Induction Electric Stoves and Gas Stoves on Energy Consumption and Their Economical Aspects (Azzahra et al., 2020), The Effect of Power Factor Improvement on the Performance of Induction Electric Stoves (Subekti, 2012), and many more technical studies of induction electric stoves.

The conversion of the use of induction electric stoves has internal and external barriers to users in Indonesia. Internally related to an increase in electric power that requires costs and an increase in cost per kwh, demands for the purchase of cooking equipment other than stoves, related to cleaning expertise and the cooking process. The user's external constraints are the reliability of the electricity network (voltage stability and unscheduled blackouts). Results require consideration of the benefits of the results obtained. This requires a theory of trying approach.

In addition to attitudes, the trait view needs to be involved. The trait is related to general self-confidence and cynicism. Cynicism is associated with views that tend to be negative for someone towards other people or the surrounding environment. Confidence will encourage someone to do an attitude that will eventually form a behavior.

Human behavior has been studied and produced a number of theories, such as: the theory of reasoned action which has been studied by Fishbein and Ajzen (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), the theory of planned behavior researched by Ajzen (Ajzen, 1988), and there is also the theory of trying which was researched by Bagozzi and Warshaw (Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990). The two theories, namely the theory of reasoned action (TRA) and the theory of planned behavior (TPB) have been applied in various fields of behavior, this is different from the theory of trying (TT). *Theory of trying* Alone intended to explain the relationship between intention and behavior by investigating people who try hard to carry out a behavior with internal and external constraints (Bagozzi & Kimmel, 1995).

The induction electric stove is a relatively new technology in Indonesia, where there are still very few users and the availability of induction electric stoves on the market is also very limited. Research on induction electric stoves can be considered as a new technology that will be adopted by society. Research like this is also carried out such as; The determinants of the online banking adoption behavior by the theory of trying in developing countries: The case of Pakistani banks (Malik et al., 2019), Explaining the adoption of mobile banking with the theory of trying, general self-confidence, and cynicism (Chaouali et al., 2017), Theory of Trying – Implications for Marketing New-concept Products (NA and M. Agarwal, 2003). Research by Malik and Chaouali together with their friends (Malik et al., 2019) and (Chaouali et al., 2017) which assumes acceptance of a new technology using Theory of Trying obtains several variables, namely; General Self-Confidence (GSC), Cynicism (CYN), Attitude Towards Success (AS), Attitude Towards Failure (AF), Attitude Towards Learning To Use New Technology (AL), Attitude Towards New Technology Adoption (AM), Intention To Adopt New Technology (IA).

The general definition of self-confidence (General Self-Confidence) is a person's attitude towards something, both a positive attitude and a negative attitude (Rosenberg, 2015). There is an opinion that self-confidence is related to individual behavior and decisions in general (Bearden et al., 2001). Confidence is also an individual's belief in being able to properly assess a decision (Tan & Tan, 2007). People who are trying for the first time and have never tried are very suitable to have general self-confidence (Ritu Agarwal et al., 2000). High self-confidence (General Self-Confidence) will certainly encourage people or someone to intend to use an induction electric stove.

Cynicism is a form of attitude that shows disbelief in a sincerity or good action or other human action that is positive towards him which then the person manifests it in the form of an attitude of doubt, distrust, contempt or ridicule. (Regoli, 1976). A low level of cynicism will encourage people or someone to intend to use an induction electric stove.

Attitude towards Trying and Succeeding/As, respondents indicated how pleasant/unpleasant and how pleasant/disgusting "trying and succeeding at losing weight over the next week will make me feel." The seven-point scale has the same response alternatives noted earlier and is also used with our Af and Ap scales (Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990, p. 134).

Attitude towards Trying and Failing (Af), subjects rated on a seven-point scale how pleasant/unpleasant and how pleasant/disgusting I would feel trying but failing to lose weight over the next week" (Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990, p. 134).

Attitude towards Process (Ap), again, with seven-point items of likeable/unfavorable and pleasant/repulsive, respondents indicated how "I try to lose weight over the next week, regardless of whether I actually lose weight." weight, will make me feel" (Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990, p. 134).

The research-related gap occurs in the attitude aspect. Chouli (2017) found that several studies are inconsistent because the concept of attitude is only one dimensional, so that multiple dimensions are needed as in the theory of trying. When it is associated with the product acceptance model according to several studies the results are also inconsistent. This is according to Faqih (2016) the reason is that in less developed countries the problem is using perceptions of product usability and ease of use instead of intention.

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Therefore this research is entitled "Intentions to Use an Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying".

1.2. Formulation of the problem

The background above which has explained the existing problems, we submit the following problem formulation, namely:

1. Does attitude toward success have a positive impact on attitudes towards induction hob adoption?
2. Do attitudes toward failure negatively impact attitudes toward adopting an induction hob?
3. Does the attitude towards learning to use an induction electric stove have a positive effect on the attitude towards the adoption of an induction electric stove?
4. Does attitude towards induction hob adoption have a positive impact on intention to adopt induction hob?
5. Does self-confidence in general have a positive impact on attitudes towards success?
6. Does self-confidence in general have a negative impact on attitudes toward failure?
7. Does self-esteem in general have a positive impact on attitudes toward learning to use an induction cooker?
8. Does cynicism have a negative impact on attitudes towards success?
9. Does cynicism have a positive impact on attitudes toward failure?
10. Does cynicism have a negative impact on attitudes toward learning to use an induction hob?
11. What is the barrier for people to switch to using an induction electric stove?

1.3. Research purposes

Based on the formulation of the problem above, the objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To analyze that the attitude towards success has a positive impact on the attitude towards the adoption of induction cookers.
2. To analyze that the attitude towards failure has a negative impact on the attitude towards the adoption of induction electric cookers.
3. To analyze that the attitude towards learning to use an induction electric stove has a positive effect on the attitude towards the adoption of an induction electric stove.
4. To analyze that the attitude towards the adoption of induction electric stove has a positive impact on the intention to adopt an induction electric stove.
5. To analyze that self-confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards success.
6. To analyze that self-confidence in general has a negative impact on attitudes towards failure.
7. To analyze that self-confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove.
8. To analyze that cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes towards success.
9. To analyze that cynicism has a positive impact on attitudes towards failure.
10. To analyze that cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric cooker.
11. To analyze people's barriers to switching to using an induction electric stove.

1.4. Benefits of research

1.4.1. Theoretical Benefits

- a. It is hoped that the general public and students who read this research will be able to add insight and knowledge about behavioral theory that has not been widely used, namely Theory of Trying.
- b. Researchers who read this research can use this research as reference material or develop this research further.

1.4.2. Practical Benefits

- a. For induction electric stove manufacturers who read this research, they can determine the right strategy to market their products so that their consumers can accept them well.
- b. For the government or other policy makers who read this research, it is hoped that it can help in making the right policies for people to switch to using induction electric stoves to reduce CO2 emissions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theory of Trying

Theory of trying intended to explain the relationship between intention and behavior by investigating people who try hard to carry out a behavior or achieve a goal, especially those that are very difficult (Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990). This means that when people try to achieve a goal they see it as a potential burden that has only the possibility of success; that is, they are concerned with the outcome (outcome) according to the sacrifices required to carry out the behavior.

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Bagozzi and Warshaw (1990), argue that goal attainment is determined by trying, namely cognitive and behavioral activities that mediate the expression of intention to achieve a goal and actual achievement. So, experiments are effective tasks that are the basis for achieving a goal (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). It is a behavior-based approach that considers one's planning to achieve far-reaching goals. This is also what is the focus of behavioral analysis on implementing rules.

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) in its development made adjustments to existing knowledge so as to produce a new theory, namely Theory of Trying (TT) namely by Bagozzi and Warshaw (Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990). Bagozzi and Warshaw changed the behavior variable in TRA to a trying variable. They postulate that attitude towards trying, social norm towards trying and frequency of past trying determine the variable intention to trying which together with the variable recency of past trying past) determines the trying variable.

In addition, the theory of attitudes in the past is considered or reviewed as only one component or unidimensional. This theory states that an attitude is not constrained by factors from within a person's self or from outside himself. This theory forms an attitude whose probability of success is higher than the probability of failure. (Taylor et al., 2001); (Xie et al., 2008)]. In contrast to the previous theory, the Theory of Trying (theory of trying) views that a person's attitude is an attitude that is influenced by many factors either from within him or outside himself or multidimensional. Bagozzi and Warshaw developed their theory to study the process of behaving when facing a problem, where a person has difficulty in determining his attitude in behaving that is influenced by internal and external factors. (Taylor et al., 2001); (Xie et al., 2008); (Al-Somali et al., 2009); (Laukkanen & Cruz, 2009); (Dey et al., 2016)]. Discussion in terms of attitudes influenced by various factors or multidimensional research has been carried out in several fields, such as in the field of entrepreneurship (Carsrud et al., 2017), the health sector, namely weight loss for diet (Bagozzi et al., 2004), attitude in adopting a technology (Ahuja & Thatcher, 2005) and many more research in other fields.

Theory of Trying or the theory of trying is different from other attitude theories, where problematic behaviors can be handled by the coexistence of a hierarchically different attitude (Bagozzi, 2007). The theory of trying a person may be able to try a particular product or service, but he does not buy or use it (Bagozzi, 1992). Meanwhile, attitudes towards a technology that is newly recognized in society is the influence of several attitudes, namely; (i) attitude towards trying and succeeding, (ii) attitude towards trying and failing, and (iii) attitude towards learning using technology [(Bagozzi, 1993); (Bagozzi, 1992); (Hinsz & Ployhart, 1998); (Xie et al., 2008)].

2.1.1. Attitude

The theory tries to conceptualize attitude as a multidimensional concept (Bagozzi et al., 1992). It is assumed that people's attitudes toward technology adoption are a function of three sub-attitudes, namely attitudes toward success, attitudes toward failure, and attitudes toward learning to use technology. The conceptualization of attitudes as a multidimensional concept seems to better explain the adoption of new technologies by consumers in developing and developing country contexts. As some experts report their adoption of this new service is faced with internal deficiencies (e.g., strong habit of gas stoves, need for new equipment and possible additional costs) as well as possible external environment (e.g., electricity infrastructure) (Akhlq and Ahmed, 2013; Cruz et al., 2010a, 2010b). Bagozzi et al. (1992) and Xie et al. (2008) further argued that individuals in developing countries will have different considerations of success, failure, and learning to use a new product.

2.2. Traits (Characteristic)

2.2.1. General self-confidence

Determining a choice, an individual can be faced with complex circumstances (Bearden et al., 2001). In these complex conditions, the role of self-confidence plays a very decisive role in making a decision. A study was produced that the attitude of an individual is determined by a self-confidence that exists in that individual (Benabou & Tirole, 2020). There are also studies that link individual self-confidence with a propensity for risk and uncertainty (Chuang et al., 2013).

The general definition of self-confidence is a person's attitude towards something, both a positive attitude and a negative attitude (Rosenberg, 2015). There is an opinion that self-confidence is related to individual behavior and decisions in general (Bearden et al., 2001). Confidence is also an individual's belief in being able to properly assess a decision (Tan & Tan, 2007). People who are trying for the first time and have never tried are very suitable to have general self-confidence (Ritu Agarwal et al., 2000).

Someone who has more general self-confidence will show himself with great self-esteem and increase his self-esteem and image. (Chuang et al., 2013), (Dodd et al., 2005)]. In uncertain situations and with all the risks, people with high self-confidence are able to make decisions, are keen to take advantage of opportunities, are confident in their choices, are able to get rid of their anxiety and overcome frustration. (Chuang et al., 2013), (Dodd et al., 2005)]. In the end, someone who has self-confidence is able to convince himself that he is able to intend to use induction cooker technology (Barber et al., 2006).

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Whereas someone who has little general self-confidence, he will tend to have a view if he is marginalized, unimportant, does not dare to take risks, thinks negatively and feels deprived, the result is uncomfortable when making a decision, lacks adaptation to change and feels that he will fail in making a decision [(Chuang et al., 2013),(Dodd et al., 2005)]. As a result, people like this do not have confidence that they are capable of intending to use induction electric stove technology(Barber et al., 2006).

Bell's research on Self-Confidence and Persuasion in Car Buying(Bell, 1967)stated that generalized confidence was measured by items used by Day and Hamblin and others(Day & Hamblin, 1964)Subjects were asked how much they agreed or disagreed with the following questions:

1. I feel capable of handling myself in most social situations.
2. I am seldom afraid that my actions will cause others to have a low opinion of me.
3. It's fine for me to enter a room where other people are already gathered and talking.
4. When in group discussions, I usually feel that my opinion is inferior.
5. I don't make a good first impression on people.
6. When confronted by a group of strangers, my first reaction is always embarrassment and low self-esteem.
7. It is very uncomfortable to accidentally go to a formal party in street clothes.
8. I don't spend a lot of time worrying about what people think of me.
9. When in a group, it is very rare to express opinions for fear of being seen as ridiculous.
10. I am never at a loss for words when I am introduced to someone.

2.2.2. Cynicism(Cynicism)

Cynicism is a form of attitude that shows disbelief in a sincerity or good action or other human action that is positive towards him, which in turn manifests it in the form of an attitude of doubt, distrust, contempt or ridicule.(Regoli, 1976).

Consumer factors to use or purchase new products or services, one of which is influenced by this cynicism [(Chylinski & Chu, 2010),(Darke & Ritchie, 2007),(Tan & Tan, 2007)]. There has been research conducted that individuals often generalize their suspicions about a product or service that they just know as a strategy of defense/defensive [(Chylinski & Chu, 2010),(Darke & Ritchie, 2007)Cynical individuals have concluded that a new product or service might feel cheated.(Chylinski & Chu, 2010),(Dean et al., 1998)]. Cynic individuals will pay more attention to the results of not using or buying a product or service that is newly known than the consequences of using or buying a new product or service. A cynical person's evaluation of failure will be greater than his or her view of success. They think that trying and failing is greater than trying and succeeding. Cynic individuals also think learning to use new products or services is useless and harmful.

Soo-Jiuan Tan and Khai-Ling Tan's research(Tan & Tan, 2007)states that in cynicism there are 7 variables, namely:

1. People would be lying if they could benefit from it.
2. People claim to have ethical standards of honesty and morality, but few adhere to them when money is at stake.
3. People pretend to care about each other more than they really do.
4. It's sad to see such an unselfish person in today's world because so many people take advantage of him.
5. Most people only care about themselves.
6. Most people at heart do not like to put themselves in the shoes of helping others.
7. Most people are dishonest by nature.

Research Taylor and his friends(Taylor et al., 2001)stating that the attitude towards success is my business and success in adopting mobile banking will make me feel ; "very unpleasant/very pleasant"; "very bad/very good"; and "very unhappy/very happy".

Research Taylor and his friends(Taylor et al., 2001)stating that the attitude towards the process is learning to use mobile banking will make me feel ; "very unpleasant/very pleasant"; "very bad/very good ; and "very unhappy/very happy".

Research Taylor and his friends(Taylor et al., 2001)stating that the attitude towards failure is that I try but fail in adopting mobile banking will make me feel ; "very unpleasant/very pleasant"; "very bad/very good"; and "very unhappy/very happy".

Research Taylor and his friends(Taylor et al., 2001)stating that the attitude towards mobile banking is adopting mobile banking will make me feel ; "very unpleasant/very pleasant"; "very bad/very good"; and "very unhappy/very pleased".

Chemingui and Ben Lallouna's research(Chemingui & Lallouna, 2013)stating that the intention to adopt online banking with statements, namely; "I plan to adopt mobile banking in the future"; "I will most likely adopt mobile banking in the future"; and "I think I'd better adopt mobile banking".

2.3. The Effect of Three Attitudes on Attitudes and Intentions To Adopt Induction Electric Stoves

There are internal barriers (risk aversion, few skills to learn new technology, distrust with government, and low levels of income, etc.) and external barriers (e.g., poor electrical infrastructure, voltage stability and unplanned or unreliable outages etc.) which makes the adoption behavior of induction electric cooker conversion problematic in less technologically developed countries

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(Ahuja & Thatcher, 2005; Chaouali et al., 2017; Alalwan et al., 2017; Roy et al., 2017; Al - Ajam & Md Nor, 2015; Akhlaq & Ahmed, 2013; Chemingui & Ben lallouna, 2013; Benamati & Serva, 2007). Therefore, the three attitudes towards the conversion of induction electric stoves are outlined in the theory of trying (attitudes towards failure, attitudes towards learning, and attitudes towards success) are heavily influenced by external and internal barriers of this kind which in turn result in overall or general attitudes towards induction hob conversion. This general attitude towards induction hobs, in turn, ultimately determines the adoption of induction hob selection behavior (Benamati & Serva, 2007; Ahuja & Thatcher, 2005; Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1990).

2.4. Previous Research

This previous research is supported by several previous studies. Table 2.1 describes some that have similarities in variables.

Table 2.1 Comparison with Previous Research

No	Researcher/ Year	VARIABLES							Research methods	Research result
		exogenous		ENDOGEN						
		X 1	X2	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5		
1	(Malik et al., 2019)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	This research method uses Structural Equation Modeling with Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM) analysis	The results show that in the developing context of Pakistan, all factors - attitudes and traits - are significant predictors of online banking adoption behavior
2	(Chaouali et al., 2017)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	This research method uses Smart PLS analysis	The results showed that the intention to adopt mobile banking was determined by attitudes towards mobile banking, which in turn were determined by attitudes towards success, attitudes towards failure, and attitudes towards learning to use mobile banking. The last three attitudes are significantly influenced by general self-confidence and cynicism
3	(Zaza & Junglas, 2016)	✓	✓				✓	✓	An exploratory study with IT professionals, along with a pre-pilot and two pilot studies to evaluate the suitability and validity of the questionnaire	The results of the study show that (a) IT self-service is a separate concept, (b) is driven by the level of IT empowerment and subjective norms, (c) manifests itself in the level of innovative work behavior.
4	(Bay & Daniel, 2003)								Preliminary analysis was conducted to test the predictive value of the three antecedent variables (attitudes toward success, attitudes toward failure, and attitudes toward	There are important differences in the results compared to previous tests of the theory tries. Most importantly, attitudes toward failure are highly significant and attitudes toward process are not.

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									process) on attitudes toward effort.	
5	(Ahuja & Thatcher, 2005)								This research method uses Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis	The results provide evidence that overload and autonomy are antecedents for trying to innovate with information technology. Furthermore, the findings confirm that autonomy interacts with overload to determine trying to innovate with IT and that this relationship varies by gender. Implications for research and practice are offered.
6	(Sandve & Øgaard, 2013)						✓		SPSS Version 19 was used for data analysis and multiple regression analysis was run to test the model.	The results show that the model receives moderate empirical support when testing the explanatory power of the theory of trying CSR decision-making processes. Attitudes toward trying, self-efficacy, subjective norms and past behavior are all to varying degrees predictors of the decision-making process,
7	(Mada, 2018)		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Method	The results of the study show that customers will have the intention to buy a new product if they have a strong motivation to achieve a certain goal, in this case trying to get good hair.
8	(Xie, 2008)		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Structural equation modeling (SEM) is used to test theoretical and general frameworks across situations and cultures. LISREL 8.54 was used for analysis.	These findings provide insight into why people prosume. The results show that global values affect domain-specific values in food perceptions. Furthermore, domain-specific values have a stronger impact on attitudes than global values and mediate the influence of global values on attitudes.
9	(Suroso, 2009)		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	<i>Elicitation study</i>	The findings show that attitudes toward success significantly influence attitudes to try at higher and lower level goals. Meanwhile, attitude towards failure does not significantly affect attitude towards trying both at lower level and higher level goals. The results also show that the intention of students at LIA to complete their studies is more influenced by external motivation, while the intention of students in trying to learn the next subject is more influenced by self-awareness.
10	(Sihombing, 2004)		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Data were analyzed with Structural Equation	Based on statistical tests, the results show that TT is more fit than TPB in explaining choosing a brand phenomenon. The results of this

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									Modeling (SEM). Maximum Likelihood (ML) is applied as a method-appropriate estimate.	study also show that direct measures and belief-based measures provide different results. However, the position taken by the researcher is to apply direct action to test the hypothesis. The reason is that these measures provide greater accuracy and reliability than belief-based measures.
11	Kurniawan(2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

Source: Summary based on several journals, data processed (2022)

Information :

- X1 : *General Self-Confidence(GSC)*
- X2 : *Cynicism(CYN)*
- Y1 : *Attitude Towards Success(US)*
- Y2 : *Attitude Towards Failure(AF)*
- Y3 : *Attitude Towards Learning To Use New Technology(AL)*
- Y4 : *Attitude Towards New Technology Adoption(AM)*
- Y5 : *Intention To Adopt New Technology(HE)*

The techniques used generally use structural equation modeling (SEM) with slight variations with regression. The use of SEM is based on covariance and component basis (PLS/partial lest square).

The location of the research was carried out in less developed countries (South Asia and the Middle East) as well as on mobile banking service products. This research directs Indonesia as a country in the Southeast Asia region.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS

3.1. conceptual framework

One of the main things in a technology acceptance model is to imagine that a view of usability and ease of use will result in a positive attitude and ultimately produce great intentions. However, this image does not apply in a poor and developing country [(Faqih, 2016),(Faqih & Jaradat, 2015)]. Meta-analysis studies have found that utilitarian understanding has a low and insignificant influence on attitudes or intentions of people in a developing country when compared to developed countries.(Schepers & Wetzels, 2007),(Yousafzai et al., 2007a),(Yousafzai et al., 2007b),(Zhang et al., 2012)].

The difference between people in developed countries with high technology and people in developing countries where technology is high is that there is a non-linear relationship between attitudes and intentions where perceived benefits and ease of use have an insignificant impact. In real terms, in developing countries there are environmental factors that hinder or harm such as the existing technological infrastructure in the country, the country's political and economic conditions.(Abou-Shouk et al., 2016),(Laukkanen & Cruz, 2009),(Cruz, Neto, et al., 2010),(Cruz, Salo, et al., 2010),(Faqih, 2016),(Faqih & Jaradat, 2015)]. Environmental problems as mentioned above will create a barrier to public acceptance of the satisfaction of consuming or using a product or service for example the convenience of using mobile banking such as access, unlimited space/can be anywhere, cost-effective and so on. Research conducted by Lee and Lu and friends(Lee & Wan, 2010)And(Lu et al., 2008), results that the acceptance of new technologies such as mobile banking is greatly affected by a mistake so that people have unfavorable attitudes and intentions for these new technological products.

Countries with low or medium per capita income, acceptance of new technologies that replace conventional or old model services is very less desirable, such as customer acceptance of mobile banking in replacing previous conventional services(Akhlaq & Ahmed, 2013),(Chemingui & Lallouna, 2013). For people who do not use a new technology product or service, there are internal and external obstacles that make the assumption that new technology products or services such as mobile banking are a problem in behaving.(Laukkanen & Kiviniemi, 2010). The above studies form the basis that the Theory of Trying is very useful in developing countries as a solution to behavior that is considered problematic. As explained in the Theory of Trying, society, in this case as consumers, has a tendency to as a whole on the acceptance of a new technology product or service based on attitudes towards success (try and succeed), attitudes towards failure (try and fail) and attitudes towards learning to accept new technology products or services.

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Figure 3.1 Conceptual Framework

Table 3.1 Source of variables in the Conceptual Framework

Variable	Source
Conceptual framework (overall)	(Chaouali et al., 2017)
General self-confidence(X1)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Zaza & Junglas, 2016)
Cynicism(X2)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Zaza & Junglas, 2016)
Attitude towards success(Y1)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Mada, 2018);(Xie, 2008);(Suroso, 2009);(Sihombing, 2004)
Attitude towards failure(Y2)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Mada, 2018);(Xie, 2008);(Suroso, 2009);(Sihombing, 2004)
Attitude towards learning(Y3)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Mada, 2018);(Xie, 2008);(Suroso, 2009);(Sihombing, 2004)
Attitude towards Induction Stove Adoption(Y4)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Zaza & Junglas, 2016);(Sandve & Øgaard, 2013);(Mada, 2018);(Xie, 2008);(Suroso, 2009);(Sihombing, 2004)
Intention to adopt Induction Stove(Y5)	(Malik et al., 2019);(Chaouali et al., 2017);(Zaza & Junglas, 2016);(Mada, 2018);(Xie, 2008);(Suroso, 2009);(Sihombing, 2004)

Source: Summary based on several journals, data processed (2022)

3.2. hypothesis

This research was conducted by researchers, having several assumptions as the grand theory of the Theory of Trying. First, if the public has a positive assessment of success, then they will tend to give an overall positive assessment of the acceptance of a new technological product or service such as an induction electric stove. But conversely, when people give a positive attitude towards a failure, they tend to give a negative assessment of the acceptance of a new technological product or service such as an induction electric stove. Furthermore, when the public or consumers have a positive attitude towards learning to use an induction electric stove, then they will have a positive attitude towards using an induction electric stove. (Reeti Agarwal et al., 2009), (Badrinarayanan et al., 2014), (Davis et al., 1989) And (Wagner et al., 2016).

Individuals with high general self-confidence show high self-esteem and increased self-image and self-esteem. (Chuang et al., 2013; Dodd et al., 2005).

H1: Attitudes toward success have a positive impact on attitudes toward induction hob adoption

H2: Attitude towards failure has a negative impact on attitude towards adoption of induction cookers

H3: Attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove have a positive effect on attitudes towards the adoption of an induction electric stove.

H4: Attitudes towards the adoption of induction hobs have a positive impact on the intention to adopt induction hobs

This research also assumes that the attitude towards the intention to use an induction electric stove is also determined by factors of self-confidence and cynicism in general. It will also discuss attitudes towards success, attitudes towards failure as well as attitudes towards learning that are influenced by self-confidence and cynicism from society or consumers in general.

Someone who feels he has more self-esteem than other people or feels his self-image is high, this is a reflection of someone's high self-confidence. (Chuang et al., 2013), (Dodd et al., 2005)]. People who have high self-confidence, have characteristics or characters capable of being decision makers, good at reading opportunities and taking advantage of them,

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accustomed to risks, confident in their choices, adaptable to uncertain environmental situations, not easily anxious or panicky and not easy to stress (Chuang et al., 2013), (Dodd et al., 2005). And finally, someone with high self-confidence will certainly be able to intend to use new technology such as induction electric stoves (Barber et al., 2006). And vice versa, for those who have low self-confidence, it will be difficult to make decisions, hesitate, worry and think that they will end in failure. Such people will not have the confidence to intend to use new technology such as induction cookers.

So that people with high self-confidence will have a positive attitude towards success, a negative attitude towards failure and a positive attitude towards learning to use new technologies such as induction electric stoves. Considering the things above, the researcher makes the following hypothesis:

H5: Confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards success.

H6: Confidence in general has a negative impact on attitudes toward failure

H7: Confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove

As self-confidence there is also another factor, namely cynicism. There are several studies that have concluded that cynicism is an important factor influencing people's or consumers' decisions to use or use relatively new technological products or services. (Chylinski & Chu, 2010), (Darke & Ritchie, 2007), (Tan & Tan, 2007). There is also research that concludes that the public or consumers are more inclined to generalize their suspicious thoughts about new technological products or services, in an attempt to survive because they are not yet familiar with these products or services. (Chylinski & Chu, 2010), (Darke & Ritchie, 2007). In addition, people or consumers who have high cynicism will conclude that they are being fooled by a new product or service, in this case the induction electric stove. (Chylinski & Chu, 2010), (Dean et al., 1998). Society or consumers who have high cynicism will tend to have a negative attitude towards success, a positive attitude towards failure and also a negative attitude towards learning to use new technology products or services such as induction electric stoves. Researchers hypothesize, as follows:

H8: Cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes towards success

H9: Cynicism has a positive effect on attitudes towards failure

H10: Cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes toward learning to use an induction hob

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Researchers in carrying out their research follow a series of processes which are all systematically interconnected, for that it requires well-planned and well-organized research stages. At each stage of the research, various theories and other research results that are relevant to the research that the researcher is conducting are used as reference material.

4.1. Types and Places of Research

4.1.1. Types of research

Researchers in conducting this study used a type of quantitative research. Quantitative research does not require detailed information, but what is needed is the quantity or amount of data that has been successfully obtained from a population under study and is expected to create the results being researched or sought. (Sugiyono, 2013).

4.1.2. Research place

For this study, researchers took the place to take samples from Indonesia in general.

4.1.3. Population and Sample Size

The definition of population is all individuals who according to researchers are taken because of certain characteristics and then analyzed to produce conclusions (Sugiyono, 2013).

The population is a combination of all elements in the form of events, things or people who have similar characteristics which are the center of attention of a researcher because they are seen as a research universe. (Ferdinand, 2006). In this research, the population is all Indonesian people who are customers of PT PLN (Persero), namely PLN household customers throughout Indonesia, totaling 75,701,985 customers.

The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2013). If the population is large, it is impossible for the researcher to study everything in the population. The sample is part of the population, consisting of several members of the population (Ferdinand, 2006).

4.2. Sampling technique

The sampling technique used in this study was non-random sampling or non-probability sampling. Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for all members or elements of the population to be sampled (Ferdinand, 2006).

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Researchers used one of the non-probability sampling techniques, namely purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a sample selected with a specific purpose or objective. Someone was chosen as the sample because the researcher considered that the person had relevant information for his research, and met the criteria set by the previous researcher (Ferdinand, 2006). The criteria used in this study are respondents or customers who use a minimum of 3,500 VA electricity or who are willing to increase their subscription power to a minimum of 3,500 VA.

Taking the number of samples has a close relationship with the SEM analysis tool. The use of SEM does not clearly determine how many samples are needed. Research Hulland and his friends (Hulland et al., 1996) revealed that the number of 100 to 200 is a sufficient number in using SEM analysis tools.

The sampling technique uses the Tora Yamane formula as in the book by Riduwan et al (Riduwan et al., 2006), that is :

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Nd^2}$$

Information:

n = the number of samples taken

N = total population (PLN household customers throughout Indonesia as many as 75,701,985 customers)

D = the precision (determination) is set at 0.1 or 10% with a 95% confidence level. The confidence interval in this study is 95 percent with a critical value of $z = 1.96$ (A. Hair et al., 2000)

$$d^2 = 0.1 \times 0.1 = 0.01$$

$$n = \frac{75.701.985}{1 + (75.701.985 \times 0,01)}$$

$$n = \frac{75.701.985}{1 + 757.019,85}$$

$$n = \frac{75.701.985}{757.020,85}$$

$$n = 99,99$$

From the results of calculations using the Tora Yamane formula, a sample of 99.99 is obtained or if it is rounded up, it is 100 samples. The researcher took a minimum sample size of 100 people because this was still within the range of 100 to 200 samples.

Researchers used an online questionnaire that is using the Google form. The online questionnaire was distributed using a social network, namely the Whatsapp application. The researcher used the Whatsapp Group (WAG) of the PLN Workers' Union, the WAG of the Indonesian Smart Energy Society (MECI), the WAG of a PLN classmate, the WAG of a classmate at the Magister of Management University of gastric Mangkurat, the Nganjuk PLN WAG, and other WAGs. The results of the questionnaire that returned were 197 respondents. After checking according to the respondent criteria required in this study, the remaining 124 respondents were processed using WARP PLS.

4.3. Research Variables and Operational Definitions of Variables

Variables are anything that is observed in a study that can be a concept that varies in value. In a study the variables used must be operationally explained. The operational concept of a variable is explained as part of a research that can explain operational variables to be observed and measured. Santoso's book explains the definition of an exogenous variable is an independent variable that affects the dependent variable. In the SEM model, these exogenous variables are marked with arrows from these variables to endogenous variables and there is no influence from other variables (Santoso, 2014). While endogenous variables are independent variables (exogenous) that affect the dependent variable. In the SEM model it is marked with an arrow pointing to the variable, where the nature of this endogenous variable is influenced and simultaneously influences other variables (Santoso, 2014). In this study there are seven variables with two exogenous variables and five endogenous variables. The table below shows the operationalization of this research, as follows:

Table 4.1 Operational Definition of General Self Confidence (GSC) Variable

Variable	Indicator	Question Items	Source
General Self-Confidence (GSC)(X1) - The general	1. Self-nature	I feel able to handle myself in most social	(Bell, 1967)
	2. Take risks	I am seldom afraid that my actions will cause others to have a low opinion of me	
	3. Dare to gather	I am confident to enter a room where other people are already gathered	

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definition of self-confidence is a person's attitude towards something, both a positive attitude and a negative attitude.	4. Role in the group	When in group discussions, my opinion is well received
	5. First	I make a good first impression on others
	6. Interaction with strangers	When dealing with a group of strangers, my first reaction is always embarrassment
	7. Official events	It's embarrassing to accidentally go to a formal event in inappropriate clothes
	8. Concern	I don't spend a lot of time worrying about what people think of me
	9. Team work	When in a group, I am very confident in expressing opinions
	10. Lots of chat	I am never at a loss for words when I am introduced to someone

Table 4.2 Variable Operationalization Cynicism(CYN)

Variable	Indicator	Question Items	Source
<i>Cynicism(CYN)(X1)</i> - is a form of attitude that shows distrust of a sincerity or good action or other positive human action towards him which then the person manifests it in the form of an attitude of doubt, distrust, contempt or ridicule.	1. Not easy to believe	I think other people will usually lie about the recognition of other people's success	(Tan & Tan, 2007)
	2. Materialistic	People claim to have ethical standards of honesty/morality, but few adhere to those ethical standards when it comes to money	
	3. Pretend	People only pretend to care more about each other when in reality it's the other way around	
	4. Selfishness	It's sad to see selfless people in today's world when so many people take advantage of them	
	5. Show yourself	Most people only stick out for themselves	
	6. Ignorance	Most people at heart do not like to put themselves in the shoes of helping others	
	7. dishonesty	Most people are dishonest by nature	

Table 4.3 Variable Operationalization Attitude Towards Success(US)

Variable	Indicator	Question Items :	Source
<i>Attitude Towards Success (USA)(Y1)</i> - Attitude is a function of beliefs about the consequences of behavior on success or normative beliefs, perceptions of the consequences of a behavior on success and assessment of behavior on success.	Pleasant	I will try and if it works using an induction hob it will make my feelings	(Taylor et al., 2001)
	Good	I will try and if it works using an induction hob it will make my feelings	
	Happy	I will try and if it works using an induction hob it will make my feelings	

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Table 4.4 Variable Operationalization Attitude Towards Failure(AF)

Variable	Indicator	Question Items :	Source
<i>Attitude Towards Failure (AF)(Y2)</i> - Attitude is a function of beliefs about the consequences of behavior towards failure or normative beliefs, perceptions of the consequences of a behavior towards failure and evaluation of behavior towards failure.	Pleasant	I will try and if it fails using an induction hob will make my feelings	(Taylor et al., 2001)
	Good	I will try and if it fails using an induction hob will make my feelings	
	Happy	I will try and if it fails using an induction hob will make my feelings	

Table 4.5 Variable Operationalization Attitude Towards Learning To Use New Technology(AL)

Variable	Indicator	Question Items :	Source
<i>Attitude Towards Learning To Use New Technology(AL)(Y3)</i> - Attitude is a function of beliefs about the consequences of behavior on learning or normative beliefs, perceptions of the consequences of a behavior on learning and assessment of behavior on learning.	Pleasant	Learning to use an induction cooker will make me feel.	(Taylor et al., 2001)
	Good	Learning to use an induction cooker will make me feel	
	Happy	Learning to use an induction cooker will make me feel	

Table 4.6 Variable Operationalization Attitude Towards New Technology Adoption(AM)

Variable	Indicator	Question Items :	Source
<i>Attitude Towards New Technology Adoption(AM)(Y4)</i> - Attitude is a function of beliefs about the consequences of behavior towards adoption or normative beliefs, perceptions of the consequences of a behavior towards adoption and judgments about behavior towards adoption.	Pleasant	Had I used an induction hob it would have made my feelings	(Taylor et al., 2001)
	Good	Had I used an induction hob it would have made my feelings	
	Happy	Had I used an induction hob it would have made my feelings	

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Table 4.7 Variable Operationalization/Intention To Adopt New Technology(HE)

Variable	Indicator	Question Items	Source
<i>Intention To Adopt New Technology(IA)(Y4)</i> - This attitude is the result of considering the loss of the intention's behavior.	Planned	I plan to use an induction hob in the future.	(Chemingui & Lallouna, 2013)
	Possibility	I will most likely use an induction hob in the future.	
	Think	I think it's better for me to use induction electric stove.	

4.4. Variable Measurement

Measurement of this variable will be carried out in a way where respondents will answer questionnaire questions by selecting the answers that have been provided from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. This is a Likert scale which has 7 choices, namely Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Somewhat Disagree, Undecided, Somewhat Agree, Agree and Strongly Agree. The answer choices on the Likert scale have a rating weight, namely:

1. Strongly Disagree (STS), has a value of 1
2. Disagree (TS), has a value of 2
3. Somewhat Disagree (ATS), has a value of 3
4. Undecided (R), weighted 4
5. Somewhat Agree (US), rated 5
6. Agree (S), has a value of 6
7. Strongly Agree (SS), has a value of 7

The method of collecting data in this study was by means of a questionnaire, namely by distributing questions to all customers of PT PLN (PERSERO) in Indonesia online using a google form by distributing the google form questionnaire link via Whatsapp (WA) social media.

4.5. Method of collecting data

This study uses primary data, namely by using a survey. The survey was carried out by the researchers directly distributing questionnaires to the respondents. The definition of a questionnaire is a tool for collecting data where the questionnaire is a collection of questions compiled by researchers to be filled in by respondents (Sugiyono, 2013).

The questionnaire uses closed questions as well as open questions, where respondents are asked to answer open and closed questions as conveyed by the researcher in the Google form link. The contents of this questionnaire have two parts, where the first part is the personal data of the respondent and the second part is related questions and research variables.

4.6. Data Analysis Techniques

4.6.1. Structural Equation Modelling

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is a multiple variable method that is capable of simultaneously analyzing both exogenous and endogenous latent variables (Bollen, 1989). SEM is capable of analyzing multiple sets of variables simultaneously, making it an efficient statistical tool to use.

SEM has characteristics where each variable influences each other, including:

1. Latent Variable

This variable is a major concern in SEM. This latent variable is a variable that is not directly measurable, for example; feelings, traits, actions or motivations.

There are two types of this latent variable, namely;

- a. Exogenous latent variable or independent latent variable, which in all equations in SEM is symbolized by a circle with an arrow facing outward. In this study, the variables General self-confidence (GSC) and Cynicism (Cyn);
- b. Endogenous latent variable or dependent latent variable, where this is symbolized by a circle with arrows facing outward and/or arrows facing inward. In this study, the variables were attitude towards success, attitude towards failure, attitude towards learning, attitude towards Induction Stove Adoption, and variables intention to adopt an induction stove (intention to use an induction electric stove).

The arrows describe a causal relationship, where the base of the arrow indicates the trigger, while the tip of the arrow indicates the effect variable.

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2. Observed Variables

This variable is a variable that can be observed or measured theoretically and pronounced as a variable. This observed variable is a dimension of a latent variable, where exogenous variables are denoted by the letter "X" and endogenous variables are denoted by the letter "Y". In this study, namely; General Self-Confidence (X1), Cynicism (X2), Attitude Towards Success (Y1), Attitude Towards Failure (Y2), Attitude Towards Learning (Y3), Attitude Towards Induction Stove Adoption (Y4) and Intention To Adopt Induction Stove (Y5)

Data analysis in this study will use software, namely WarpPLS.

4.6.2. Reasons for Using the Method

This study uses SEM with the consideration that the SEM method is able to analyze the relationship of two or more variables where some of them are variables that can be measured directly or indirectly. On the other hand, this research also looks for the relationship between variables and their dominant indicators.

SEM is used in this study with the following considerations; (1) This study examines the relationship between constructs to test the theory. This is very appropriate because SEM is a confirmation technique (Fidell et al., 1996) which is based on a theory-based approach (Bentler PM & Chou Chih-Ping, 1987); (Aaker & Bagozzi, 1979). Analysis in SEM includes analysis that has links including theory, methodology and statistics (Bagozzi, 1981); (2) SEM is able to measure the relationship between latent variables and variables that are directly observed (Hoyle & Panther, 1995); (3) Errors in measurement can be controlled with SEM which ultimately can be tested without bias the relationship between constructs (MacKenzie, 2001) & (Steenkamp & Baumgartner, 1998).

4.7. Outer model test (Validity and Reliability Test)

The outer model test is an indicator test related to latent variables. The result is to determine whether the indicator can be continued in the calculation and analysis of the inner model. Two tests, namely the Validity Test and Reliability Test to evaluate the measurement scale used.

4.7.1. Validity test

To measure the ability of the questionnaire to be able or not to explain the meaning or purpose contained in the questionnaire, a validity test was used (Ghozali & Latan, 2015, p. 45). Validity can be measured by construct validity test, namely Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

Convergent validity is declared passed if the loading value is at least 0.5 and the significant value (p value) is below the maximum 0.05 (Kock, 2020, p. 87). Requirements that must be met loading factor must be significant, then the standardized loading estimate must be equal to 0.50 or more and ideally it must be 0.70 (Ghozali, 2008). This states that the indicators used are valid to measure what should be measured in the research model.

Discriminant validity is a way of assessing how different a construct is from another construct, which can be determined by comparing the AVE values of the two constructs with the squared value of the correlation between the two constructs tested. Discriminant validity is measured from the average variance extracted (AVE) value. The size used is a value greater than 0.5 (Joe F. Hair et al., 2014).

4.7.2. Reliability Test

A data collection tool or questionnaire is declared reliable or reliable if the respondent's answers about a statement in the questionnaire are consistent from time to time. In SEM, high reliability indicates that indicators have high consistency in measuring their latent constructs. Reliability in PLS can be known through Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Application. The Composite Reliability value is said to be good if it has a value > 0.7 . An indicator is said to have good indicator reliability against its construct if the outer loading value is ≥ 0.70 . Construct reliability can also be seen from the Cronbach's Alpha value, if the value is > 0.7 (Joe F. Hair et al., 2010). Kock (2020) adds that the criteria can be at least 0.6.

4.8. Latent Variable Descriptive Analysis

Data that has been collected from the results of the questionnaire filled out by respondents on a Likert scale will be given a value according to the respondent's answer. The results of the respondents' answers will give effect to each variable, both independent and dependent. This study used loading analysis and item contributions to latent variables. This was chosen according to the rules of the structural approach. Loading and item contributions take the average and standard deviation values into account in the calculations.

The measure of the value of the indicator item on the latent variable uses the calculation results in the indicator weight table (Kock, 2020, pp. 90-92). The concern is on value *Indicator weight-loading signs* (WLS), and Effect sizes (ES). WLS must have a positive value, meaning it shows a positive contribution to the indicator R squared. ES is the indicator's contribution to R squared. The ES value must be above 0.02, below that it cannot be used in practice.

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4.9. Outlier Test

There are four types of outliers (JF Hair et al., 1995), namely: (1) outliers caused by errors in entering data; (2) outliers due to the emergence of explainable extremes; (3) outliers that arise due to extreme things that cannot be explained; and (4) outliers that arise due to combination with other variables in the study.

This study will carry out an outlier test which will begin by testing the univariate distribution of each variable. Outliers are declared to exist if there are observations that fall outside the distribution range. The criterion is that any standardized variable value that exceeds 4 is an outlier (JF Hair et al., 1995).

Multivariately Wasserman (2022) explains the need for diagrams. scatter to see it. Table 4.1 shows the four data patterns. The lower right image shows the outliers that affect the model. Other patterns don't show problematic outliers. Especially the top right pattern shows non-linear symptoms. Non-linear requires different techniques or indications of other variables that change the direction of influence.

Figure 4.1 Multivariate Outlier Pattern

4.10. Model Fit and Goodness Test

The PLS warp used as an analysis tool requires 10 criteria that must be met by a model so that it can be said to be good for use in examining the variables used. Goodness of fit (GoF) test is used to test the inner model. Table 4.8. display GoF criteria and quality indices.

Table 4.8 Model of Fit and Quality Indices

No	Indikasi Model fit & Quality Indices	Kriteria Fit
1	Average Path Coefficient (APC)	$p < 0.05$
2	Average R-squared (ARS)	$p < 0.05$
3	Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)	$p < 0.05$
4	Average Block VIF (AVIF)	diterima jika ≤ 5 , idealnya ≤ 3.3
5	Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	diterima jika ≤ 5 , idealnya ≤ 3.3
6	Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	Kecil ≥ 0.1 Medium ≥ 0.25 Besar ≥ 0.36
7	Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.7 , idealnya = 1
8	R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.9 , idealnya = 1
9	Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.7
10	Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.7

Source: (cock, 2020)

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4.11. Inner Model Test (Hypothesis and Effect Size)

The inner model test is related to the hypothesis testing of the research. Direction of influence and significant value can be analyzed. Influence can be positive or negative from exogenous variables to endogenous. The significant value used is a maximum of 0.05 (Kock, 2020, pp. 82-83).

The inner model test also involves Effect Size (ES) to see the contribution of each path to R Squared (Cock, 2020, pp. 84-85). The pathway in question is the pathway of the explanatory in the endogenous variables AS, AF and AL. The next line is the one that goes to AM. The last path is the path to IA.

4.12. Determination Coefficient Test

R Squared or the coefficient of determination is also used (Kock, 2020, p. 94). This is to see how much the ability of the endogenous variables is explained by the predictor variables. The rest is explained by other variables not involved in the study. This is important for evaluating the power of the model and possibly considering other variables in practice.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. General Description of the Research Object

5.1.1. Research Object Identity

This study chose respondents, namely household customers of PT PLN (Persero) throughout Indonesia where a total of 75,701,985 customers had a subscription power of 3500 VA or other subscription power who were willing to increase the power to 3500 VA and above. General criteria for respondents, namely gender is not limited, domicile in all provinces in Indonesia, age from 18 years to more than 54 years, marital status is not limited, education from elementary school to doctoral degree or other, type of work is not limited, and PLN subscription power from 450 VA up to more than 3500 VA.

5.2. Description of Respondents

5.2.1. Gender

The gender of the respondents in Table 5.1 is mostly male (69%), female (30%), and 1% of respondents who did not fill in. The online questionnaire using the Google form is not specific to a particular gender because it is distributed using the WhatsApp (WA) application. The majority of respondents were male, naturally even though it was not intentional because the researchers used a network of friends of researchers who hung out more with male friends.

Table 5.1 Gender of Respondents

Jenis Kelamin	Frekuensi	Presentasi
Pria	86	69%
Wanita	37	30%
Tidak Mengisi	1	1%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.2. domicile

The results of the questionnaires that were distributed by researchers online, obtained data that the questionnaires were filled in by respondents from 18 provinces in Indonesia from 34 existing provinces. Table 5.2 can be seen that the majority of respondents live in South Kalimantan as much as 40.32%, this is influenced by the researcher's domicile in Banjarbaru, South Kalimantan. There are many WAG researchers with networks around South Kalimantan and Central Kalimantan which are the research work areas, namely PT PLN (Persero) Main Unit Distribution of South Kalimantan and Central Kalimantan.

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Table 5.2 Respondent's domicile

No	Domisili	Frekuensi	Presentasi
1	Nusa tenggara Timur	1	0,81%
2	Bangka Belitung	1	0,81%
3	Sulawesi Tengah	1	0,81%
4	DI Yogyakarta	1	0,81%
5	Lampung	1	0,81%
6	Kalimantan Barat	1	0,81%
7	Jawa Tengah	1	0,81%
8	Sulawesi Selatan	2	1,61%
9	Kalimantan Timur	2	1,61%
10	Papua	3	2,42%
11	Banten	5	4,03%
12	Jawa Barat	5	4,03%
13	Sulawesi Utara	7	5,65%
14	Kalimantan Tengah	8	6,45%
15	Jawa Timur	10	8,06%
16	DKI Jakarta	12	9,68%
17	Nusa tenggara Barat	12	9,68%
18	Kalimantan Selatan	50	40,32%
19	Tidak Mengisi	1	0,81%
Jumlah		124	100,00%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.3. Age

Table 5.3 can be seen that the majority of respondents are aged between 36-44 years by 32% and between 27-35 years by 31%. This is also in line with the status of respondents who are married as much as 86% as shown in table 5.4. The age range from 27 to 44 years is the normal age for marriage/marriage.

Table 5.3 Age of Respondents

Umur	Frekuensi	Presentasi
18 - 26 Tahun	11	9%
27 -35 Tahun	39	31%
36 - 44 Tahun	40	32%
45 - 53 Tahun	29	23%
Lebih 54 Tahun	5	4%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.4. Marital status

Respondents in table 5.4 show that 86% of respondents are married, as explained above in line with the age of the respondents, which is a normal age for marriage in Indonesia.

Table 5.4 Marital Status

Status	Frekuensi	Presentasi
Kawin	107	86%
Tidak Kawin	16	13%
Tidak Mengisi	1	1%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.5. Education

The educational level of the respondents, as shown in table 5.5, varied from junior high school or its equivalent to master's or equivalent, where the majority were bachelor's or equivalent education at 62%. With the education level of the majority S1 or equivalent, it is expected that filling out the questionnaire can meet the expectations of the researcher.

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Table 5.5 Level of Education

Pendidikan	Frekuensi	Presentasi
SD atau Sederajat	0	0%
SMP atau Sederajat	0	0%
SMA atau Sederajat	22	18%
S1 atau Sederajat	77	62%
S2 atau Sederajat	20	16%
S3 atau Sederajat	0	0%
Lainnya	5	4%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.6. Work

The distribution of the types of work of the respondents is in table 5.6 where the majority are other jobs of 52%, this is also in line with the education of the respondents, the majority of whom are S1 or equivalent, all have jobs other than the type of work that exists (Students/students, ASN or PNS, Private Workers, Employees freelancing, and self-employed).

Table 5.6 Types of Work

Pekerjaan	Frekuensi	Presentasi
Pelajar/mahasiswa	2	2%
ASN atau PNS	19	15%
Pekerja Swasta	28	23%
Pekerja Lepas	1	1%
Wiraswasta	9	7%
lainnya	65	52%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.7. Respondents Subscription Power

Table 5.7 shows the subscription power owned by respondents, where the majority are more than 3500 VA by 43%. This is highly expected by researchers because respondents in infrastructure have the ability to use induction electric stoves, this is in accordance with the data of respondents who know about induction electric stoves as shown in table 5.8 as much as 96%.

Table 5.7 Respondents' Electrical Power

Daya Langgan	Frekuensi	Presentasi
450 VA	3	2%
900 VA	21	17%
1300 VA	17	14%
2200 VA	28	23%
lebih 3500 VA	53	43%
Tidak mengisi	2	2%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.2.8. Knowledge of induction electric stoves

Table 5.8 shows the respondents' knowledge about induction electric stoves, where the majority of respondents know about 96% of induction electric stoves. This is in accordance with the respondent's subscription power above 3500 VA as shown in table 5.7. Table 5.8 Knowledge of induction electric stoves

Pengetahuan Kompiler Induksi	Frekuensi	Presentasi
Ya	119	96%
Tidak	5	4%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

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5.2.9. Willingness Up Power

Table 5.9 shows that many respondents are willing to increase their subscription power to above 3500 VA by 86%. This is in line with the education level of the respondents as shown in table 5.5 which has insight into the benefits of using electricity by increasing electric power.

Table 5.9 Willingness to Power Up

Kesediaan	Frekuensi	Presentasi
Ya	107	86%
Tidak	16	13%
Tidak mengisi	1	1%
Jumlah	124	100%

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.3. Outer Model Test

5.3.1. validity

The first thing to note is validity. If the validity does not pass, the modeling and calculations must be repeated. Table 5.10 provides an overview of the initial stages of modeling and calculation. The convergent validity criterion used is a minimum loading value of 0.5 and a significant value (p value) below a maximum of 0.05 (Kock, 2020, p. 87). The results show that the X1.7 indicator related to the GSC variable does not pass the convergent validity test because the loading value is less than 0.5, namely 0.098 and the p value is above 0.05, namely 0.134. For other indicators besides X1.7, all of them have a loading value above 0.5 and a p value <0.001.

Table 5.10 Value of Combined loadings and cross-loadings Stage 1

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA	P value
X1.1	0.583	0.210	0.060	0.032	0.604	-0.613	-0.054	<0.001
X1.2	0.595	-0.104	0.403	0.098	0.215	-0.576	0.095	<0.001
X1.3	0.748	-0.029	-0.004	0.003	0.360	-0.242	-0.027	<0.001
X1.4	0.619	0.204	0.107	-0.247	0.397	-0.667	-0.095	<0.001
X1.5	0.789	-0.000	0.044	0.030	-0.063	0.120	-0.002	<0.001
X1.6	0.822	-0.067	-0.172	0.108	-0.102	0.320	-0.061	<0.001
X1.7	0.098	0.015	-0.417	0.257	-0.457	0.678	0.089	0.134
X1.8	0.651	0.010	0.010	-0.091	-0.247	0.195	0.139	<0.001
X1.9	0.830	-0.104	-0.236	-0.078	-0.276	0.336	0.140	<0.001
X1.10	0.862	-0.035	-0.002	0.070	-0.494	0.538	-0.127	<0.001
X2.1	0.254	0.641	-0.037	0.097	-0.258	0.336	-0.296	<0.001
X2.2	-0.108	0.656	0.572	0.099	-0.256	-0.092	-0.095	<0.001
X2.3	-0.119	0.815	-0.129	0.020	-0.131	0.381	0.006	<0.001
X2.4	0.098	0.720	0.181	-0.128	-0.046	-0.120	-0.045	<0.001
X2.5	0.024	0.845	0.117	-0.110	0.141	-0.333	0.103	<0.001
X2.6	-0.085	0.812	-0.263	0.034	0.114	0.012	0.201	<0.001
X2.7	-0.024	0.683	-0.383	0.020	0.384	-0.158	0.043	<0.001
Y1.1	-0.014	-0.005	0.981	-0.013	0.052	-0.024	0.047	<0.001
Y1.2	-0.002	-0.015	0.981	0.053	-0.091	0.065	-0.055	<0.001
Y1.3	0.017	0.020	0.970	-0.040	0.040	-0.042	0.008	<0.001
Y2.1	0.021	0.030	-0.064	0.948	-0.052	0.131	0.020	<0.001
Y2.2	-0.017	0.001	0.043	0.980	-0.082	0.024	0.029	<0.001
Y2.3	-0.003	-0.031	0.020	0.970	0.133	-0.152	-0.049	<0.001
Y3.1	-0.004	-0.012	0.051	0.039	0.945	0.034	-0.065	<0.001
Y3.2	0.026	0.011	-0.000	-0.006	0.970	0.078	0.016	<0.001
Y3.3	-0.022	0.001	-0.050	-0.032	0.962	-0.112	0.048	<0.001
Y4.1	-0.034	-0.007	-0.001	0.069	-0.043	0.932	-0.131	<0.001
Y4.2	-0.006	0.012	-0.053	-0.047	0.069	0.959	-0.012	<0.001
Y4.3	0.040	-0.005	0.054	-0.021	-0.027	0.948	0.141	<0.001
Y5.1	-0.029	0.008	0.097	-0.009	-0.022	-0.204	0.969	<0.001
Y5.2	0.002	0.019	0.095	-0.020	0.012	-0.243	0.970	<0.001
Y5.3	0.031	-0.031	-0.214	0.032	0.011	0.500	0.866	<0.001

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

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From the results of the first stage of calculations, where the X1.7 indicator did not pass convergent validity, a re-calculation was carried out by eliminating the X1.7 indicator, resulting in the calculation as shown in table 5.11. The results of the second stage of the calculation obtained the loading value of all indicators above 0.5 and the p value <0.001. Thus after the calculation of stage II, convergent validity passed.

Table 5.11 Value of Combined loadings and cross-loadings Stage 2

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA	P value
X1.1	0.586	0.210	0.039	0.043	0.560	-0.557	-0.054	<0.001
X1.2	0.596	-0.104	0.399	0.100	0.214	-0.573	0.096	<0.001
X1.3	0.746	-0.030	0.007	-0.003	0.396	-0.286	-0.025	<0.001
X1.4	0.618	0.203	0.114	-0.251	0.425	-0.701	-0.093	<0.001
X1.5	0.791	0.000	0.022	0.042	-0.110	0.180	-0.002	<0.001
X1.6	0.823	-0.067	-0.185	0.116	-0.126	0.351	-0.060	<0.001
X1.8	0.650	0.010	0.010	-0.091	-0.240	0.187	0.141	<0.001
X1.9	0.829	-0.104	-0.243	-0.073	-0.284	0.348	0.141	<0.001
X1.10	0.861	-0.035	-0.009	0.074	-0.502	0.550	-0.125	<0.001
X2.1	0.249	0.641	-0.029	0.093	-0.234	0.306	-0.295	<0.001
X2.2	-0.091	0.656	0.541	0.116	-0.335	0.007	-0.097	<0.001
X2.3	-0.130	0.815	-0.109	0.009	-0.081	0.317	0.007	<0.001
X2.4	0.103	0.720	0.171	-0.122	-0.072	-0.088	-0.045	<0.001
X2.5	0.031	0.845	0.103	-0.102	0.107	-0.290	0.103	<0.001
X2.6	-0.092	0.812	-0.250	0.027	0.143	-0.025	0.201	<0.001
X2.7	-0.030	0.683	-0.372	0.014	0.410	-0.190	0.044	<0.001
Y1.1	-0.015	-0.005	0.981	-0.014	0.055	-0.027	0.047	<0.001
Y1.2	-0.003	-0.015	0.981	0.052	-0.089	0.063	-0.055	<0.001
Y1.3	0.018	0.020	0.970	-0.039	0.035	-0.036	0.008	<0.001
Y2.1	0.017	0.030	-0.057	0.948	-0.032	0.106	0.021	<0.001
Y2.2	-0.016	0.001	0.041	0.980	-0.086	0.029	0.029	<0.001
Y2.3	-0.000	-0.030	0.014	0.970	0.118	-0.133	-0.050	<0.001
Y3.1	-0.003	-0.012	0.049	0.041	0.945	0.042	-0.065	<0.001
Y3.2	0.025	0.011	0.000	-0.006	0.970	0.077	0.016	<0.001
Y3.3	-0.023	0.001	-0.048	-0.034	0.962	-0.119	0.048	<0.001
Y4.1	-0.033	-0.007	-0.002	0.070	-0.046	0.932	-0.131	<0.001
Y4.2	-0.006	0.012	-0.053	-0.047	0.068	0.959	-0.012	<0.001
Y4.3	0.039	-0.005	0.055	-0.021	-0.024	0.948	0.141	<0.001
Y5.1	-0.028	0.009	0.095	-0.008	-0.027	-0.197	0.969	<0.001
Y5.2	0.002	0.019	0.095	-0.020	0.012	-0.243	0.970	<0.001
Y5.3	0.030	-0.031	-0.212	0.031	0.016	0.493	0.866	<0.001

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

The next discriminant validity is measured from the average variance extracted (AVE) value. The size used is a value greater than 0.5 (Kock, 2020, p. 94). Table 5.12 shows that all latent variables have a value of more than 0.5. This shows that the model passes the discriminant validity test.

Table 5.12 Value of Average variances extracted (AVE)

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
0.532	0.552	0.955	0.934	0.920	0.897	0.877

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

The second discriminant validity is that the AVE root value must be higher than the latent variable correlation. The root value of AVE lies in the diagonal value of 0.730; 0.743; 0.977; 0.966; 0.959; 0.947 and 0.936. Table 5.13 shows that the diagonal value is higher than the correlation value on the latent variable (related column).

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Table 5.13 Correlations among I.vs. with sq. rts. of AVEs

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
GSC	0.730	-0.054	0.513	-0.098	0.501	0.494	0.352
CYN	-0.054	0.743	-0.044	0.198	-0.009	-0.037	0.033
AS	0.513	-0.044	0.977	-0.203	0.800	0.799	0.611
AF	-0.098	0.198	-0.203	0.966	-0.158	-0.194	0.016
AL	0.501	-0.009	0.800	-0.158	0.959	0.848	0.517
AM	0.494	-0.037	0.799	-0.194	0.848	0.947	0.619
IA	0.352	0.033	0.611	0.016	0.517	0.619	0.936

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

Predictive validity is measured by the value of Q square or blindfolding. The size used is a value greater than 0 (kock, 2020, p. 95). Table 5.14 shows that all endogenous variables have values above 0. The model passes predictive validity.

Table 5.14 Value of Q-squared coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
		0.345	0.076	0.335	0.808	0.398

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.3.2. Reliability

The model must pass the composite reliability test and cronbach's alpha. The ideal value for both is at least 0.7 although it is accepted if it is at least 0.6. Table 5.15 shows that the composite reliability value is above 0.7 and table 5.16 also shows that the Cronbach's alpha value is also above 0.7, so the second model passes the reliability test.

Table 5.15 Composite reliability coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
0.909	0.895	0.985	0.977	0.972	0.963	0.955

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

Table 5.16 Value of Cronbach's alpha coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
0.886	0.862	0.977	0.965	0.956	0.942	0.928

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

After testing the validity and reliability, the best model obtained for this study is as shown in Figure 5.1 by eliminating X1.7.

5.4. Latent Variable Descriptive Analysis

5.4.1. Description of Research variables

The average value is shown in Table 5.17 Mean 7 Research Variables. The highest average is the intention to adopt. The lowest is the variable attitude towards failure and cynicism. The mean value of a scale of 7 indicates a critical point is 4 related to tend to enter disapproval or unhappiness. The five variables above the four biggest critical points are intention of adoption, attitude towards adoption, attitude towards success and attitude towards learning.

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Table 5.17 Average of 7 Research Variables

Variabel	Rata-rata
GSC	5,48
Sinisme	3,91
<i>Attitude towards Success</i>	5,79
<i>Attitude towards Failure</i>	3,44
<i>Attitude towards Learning</i>	5,79
<i>Attitude towards Adoption</i>	5,83
<i>Intention of Adoption</i>	5,86

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

Two variables tend to be experienced low by respondents. This is related to values below 4, namely cynicism and attitude towards failure. This means that these two variables were not experienced by the respondents. People tend not to be cynical about the government and failures do not affect the perceptions of respondents.

5.4.2. Description of Indicator Strength

The test looks at the ES and WLS values in the indicator weight table. Table 5.18 displays the results of the calculations. WLS all indicators are positive. ES value above 0.02. This means that all indicators contribute to the ability to explain the model (R Squared). The lowest ES on the X1.1 indicator is 0.072. The indicators that give the biggest contribution are the variable indicators of attitude towards success, attitude towards failure, attitude towards learning, attitude towards adoption and intention to adopt.

Table 5.18 Value of Indicator weights

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA	WLS	ES
X1.1	0.122	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.072
X1.2	0.124	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.074
X1.3	0.156	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.116
X1.4	0.129	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.080
X1.5	0.165	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.131
X1.6	0.172	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.141
X1.8	0.136	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.088
X1.9	0.173	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.143
X1.10	0.180	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.155
X2.1	0.000	0.166	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.107
X2.2	0.000	0.170	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.111
X2.3	0.000	0.211	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.172
X2.4	0.000	0.186	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.134
X2.5	0.000	0.219	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.185
X2.6	0.000	0.210	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.171
X2.7	0.000	0.177	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.121
Y1.1	0.000	0.000	0.342	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.336
Y1.2	0.000	0.000	0.342	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.336
Y1.3	0.000	0.000	0.338	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.328
Y2.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.338	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.321
Y2.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.350	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.343
Y2.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.346	0.000	0.000	0.000	1	0.336
Y3.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.343	0.000	0.000	1	0.324
Y3.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.351	0.000	0.000	1	0.341
Y3.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.349	0.000	0.000	1	0.335
Y4.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.347	0.000	1	0.323
Y4.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.357	0.000	1	0.342
Y4.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.353	0.000	1	0.334
Y5.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.369	1	0.357
Y5.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.369	1	0.357
Y5.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.329	1	0.285

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

GSC (general self-confident) variables sequentially contributing to R Square are indicators X1.10, X1.9, X1.6, X1.5, X1.3, X1.8, X1.4, X1.2, and X1.1. The Cyn variable (cynicism) sequentially the indicator contribution is X2.5, X2.3, X2.6, X2.4, X2.7, X2.2, and X2.1. Attitude towards success variables respectively are Y1.1, Y1.2, and Y1.3. Attitudes towards failure are Y2.2, Y2.3, and Y2.1.

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Attitudes towards learning are Y3.2, Y3.3, and Y3.1. Attitudes towards the adoption of electric induction cookers are Y4.2, Y4.3, and Y4.1. The intention to adopt the stove is Y5.1, Y5.2, and Y5.3. This sequence is important in policy priorities. This also applies to the order of other variables.

5.4.3. General Self-Confidence (GSC) Indicator Description

All GSC indicators exceed critical values. Only one under it, namely X1.7, is a matter of dressing. The highest indicator is a positive impression on the people you meet. From Table 5.19 it shows that GSC is indeed experienced by respondents with an average score of 5.48.

Table 5.19 Average GSC Indicators

Indikator GSC	Rata-rata
X1.1	5,99
X1.2	5,41
X1.3	5,61
X1.4	5,60
X1.5	6,02
X1.6	5,57
X1.7	3,57
X1.8	5,56
X1.9	5,81
X1.10	5,66

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.4.4. Cynicism Indicator Description (CYN)

CYN generally did not occur in respondents. This can be seen in Table 5.20, where all indicators are still around critical point 4. Only two indicators can be said to have occurred, namely the perception that many people are used by other people and that many people are arrogant or self-assertive.

Table 5.20 Average CYN Indicators

Indikator CYN	Rata-rata
X2.1	3,30
X2.2	4,67
X2.3	3,89
X2.4	4,44
X2.5	4,30
X2.6	3,40
X2.7	3,40

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.4.5. Attitude Towards Success (US) Indicator Description

AS did occur in respondents. Table 5.21 shows all the indicators above 4. Success is more related to goodness and happiness.

Table 5.21 Average US Indicators

Indikator AS	Rata-rata
Y1.1	5,81
Y1.2	5,82
Y1.3	5,74

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.4.6. Attitude Towards Failure (AF) Indicator Description

Regarding AF, it can be seen in Table 5.22. Value below 4 even though feeling good reaches 3.504. This means that failure will have a negative impact on feelings.

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Table 5.22 Average AF Indicator

Indikator AF	Rata-rata
Y2.1	3,50
Y2.2	3,38
Y2.3	3,44

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.4.7. Attitude Towards Learning (AL) Indicator Description

The AL indicator shows the average above 4. Table 5.23 shows the average above 5. The feelings that occur are positive towards happiness.

Table 5.23 Average LA Indicator

Indikator AL	Rata-rata
Y3.1	5,78
Y3.2	5,81
Y3.3	5,78

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.4.8. Description of Attitude Towards Induction Stove Adoption (AM) Indicator

AM indicates a value above 5. Table 5.24 shows this and is almost evenly distributed. Attitudes towards the adoption of induction cookers tend to give positive perceptions.

Table 5.24 Mean AM Indicators

Indikator AM	Rata-rata
Y4.1	5,80
Y4.2	5,82
Y4.3	5,87

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.4.9. Description of Intention to adopt Induction Stove (IA) Indicator

The IA indicator is also above the critical value of 4. Table 5.25 shows the value above 5. The desire for adoption is also evenly distributed in each indicator on a scale of 6. This means that the desire for adoption is approved by the respondents.

Table 5.25 Average of IA Indicators

Indikator IA	Rata-rata
Y5.1	5,86
Y5.2	5,82
Y5.3	5,90

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.5. Outlier Test

The outlier test results for each variable show two things. This can be seen in table 5.26. Variables that contain outlier values (minimum or maximum values) are success attitudes and learning attitudes. The minimum score is above 4. However, it is still below 5. Outlier values that have an effect are extreme values. The value 4 is not skipped by only a few digits.

Table 5.26 Latent variable coefficients

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
Min	-3.140	-2.334	-4.407	-1.578	-4.488	-1.867	-3.158
Max	1.489	2.464	1.078	2.315	1.099	1.165	0.991

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

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5.6. Model Conformity and Quality Test

Table 5.27 shows the 10 criteria for model fit and quality indices to produce fit results. This shows that all criteria are still within the allowable value limits. This shows that the model is good and all endogenous variables can be explained by exogenous variables.

Table 5.27 Results of Fit & Quality Indices Models

No	Indikasi Model fit & Kualitas	Kriteria Fit	Hasil
1	Average path coefficient (APC)=0.329	$p < 0.05$	$P < 0.001$
2	Average R-squared (ARS)=0.372	$p < 0.05$	$P < 0.001$
3	Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)=0.362	$p < 0.05$	$P < 0.001$
4	Average block VIF (AVIF)	diterima jika ≤ 5 , idealnya ≤ 3.3	1.498
5	Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	diterima jika ≤ 5 , idealnya ≤ 3.3	2.591
6	Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	Kecil ≥ 0.1 Medium ≥ 0.25 Besar ≥ 0.36	0.549
7	Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.7 , idealnya = 1	0.800
8	R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.9 , idealnya = 1	0.969
9	Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.7	1.000
10	Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	Diterima jika ≥ 0.7	0.900

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

5.7. Inner Model Test (Hypothesis Test and Effect Size)

Direction of influence and significant value (p value) can be seen in Table 5.28 and table 5.29. Directions and significant details per hypothesis are as follows:

Table 5.28 Path coefficients

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
AS	0.528	-0.133					
AF	-0.147	0.186					
AL	0.517	0.143					
AM			0.370	0.034	0.600		
IA						0.628	

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

Table 5.29 P Value

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
AS	<0.001	0.064					
AF	0.046	0.016					
AL	<0.001	0.051					
AM			<0.001	0.353	<0.001		
IA						<0.001	

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

H1: Attitudes toward success have a positive impact on attitudes toward induction hob adoption

Hypothesis 1 proved positive with a coefficient value of 0.370 and a significant value below 0.05.

H2: Attitudes toward failure have a negative impact on attitudes toward induction hob adoption

Hypothesis 2 was not proven negative and not significant. This can be seen from the positive coefficient value of 0.034 and a significant value above 0.05, namely 0.353.

The outlier test shows that the data reveals no outliers. The data pattern shows that the data is spread very far. Figure 5.2 Scatter Diagram and Data Pattern Line shows these two things. None of the data ranges exceed 4 standard deviations. The pattern side shows that there is no good data collection pattern.

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Figure 5.2 Scatter Diagram and Pattern Lines of AF and AM Data
Source: Primary data processed in 2023

The slightly curved pattern of the data pattern lines indicates that there are two patterns. Figure 5.3 Focus The AF and AM patterns show one positive relationship and one negative pattern.

Figure 5.3 AF and AM Focus Patterns

The researcher found the fact that there were variables that changed direction and weakened the effect of failure attitudes and adoption attitudes, influenced by the attitude of indifference or indifference of respondents about the attitude towards failure variable (AF) as shown in table 5.20. While the response of respondents to the adoption variable (AM) was quite enthusiastic as shown in table 5.22.

Online questionnaires are very different from offline, where researchers can interact directly with respondents. Online questionnaires also require clear explanations or descriptions so that respondents who do not meet face to face with researchers can understand the questions in the questionnaire so that they can provide clearer responses to these variables. There are three reasons why the respondent answered neutral or doubtful, namely; (1) the respondent has no attitude or opinion, (2) the

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respondent gives a balanced score, and (3) the respondent does not yet have a clear attitude or opinion (Shaw & Wright, 1967). In addition, there are other factors that influence respondents, such as doubt or not understanding the intent of the questions in the questionnaire (Kulas & Stachowski, 2009).

H3: Attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove have a positive effect on attitudes towards the adoption of an induction electric stove.

Hypothesis 3 is proven positive and significant. This can be seen from the coefficient value of 0.600 and significantly below 0.05.

H4: Attitudes towards the adoption of induction hobs have a positive impact on the intention to adopt induction hobs

Hypothesis 4 proved positive and significant. This can be seen from the coefficient value of 0.628 and a significant value below 0.05.

H5: Confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards success.

Hypothesis 5 on self-esteem in general is positive and significant. This can be seen from the coefficient value of 0.528 and a significant value of less than 0.05

H6: Confidence in general has a negative impact on attitudes toward failure

Hypothesis 6 proved to be negative and significant. This can be seen from the coefficient value -0.147 and the significant value is at 0.046.

H7: Confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove

Hypothesis 7 proved to be significant and positive. This corresponds to a coefficient value of 0.517 and a significant value below 0.05.

H8: Cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes towards success

Hypothesis 8 proved to be significant and negative. The coefficient value is -0.133 and the significant value is at 0.064.

H9: Cynicism has a positive effect on attitudes towards failure

Hypothesis 9 proved to be significant and positive. The coefficient value is 0.186 and it is significant at 0.016.

H10: Cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes toward learning to use an induction hob

Hypothesis 10 does not prove negative but is significant. This shows a coefficient of 0.143 and a significant value of 0.051.

Checks were also carried out regarding outliers and data patterns related to differences in results with theory. There were indeed outliers at one point because the standard value exceeded 4. However, judging from the significant value, this was not a problem. It can be seen from the distribution of the data that the distribution is not a problem. The problem lies in the data pattern line.

Figure 5.4 Scatter Diagram and Lines of Cyn and AL Data Patterns

The focus on influence shows similarities to the previous problem. Figure 5.5 Focus on the relationship between CYN and AL shows two patterns. This describes the symptoms of differences in the characteristics of the respondents. But this is more to other variables that change the direction of influence.

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Figure 5.5 Focus on CYN and AL Relations

Researchers found the fact that there were variables that changed direction and weakened the effect of cynicism and attitudes towards learning, influenced by the attitude of indifference or indifference of respondents about the variable cynicism (CYN) as shown in table 5.18. While the response of respondents to the learning variable (AL) was quite enthusiastic as shown in table 5.21.

The explanation is the same as the unproven Hypothesis 2 (H2) above that online questionnaires also require clear explanations or descriptions so that respondents who do not meet face to face with researchers can understand the questions in the questionnaire so that they can provide clearer responses to variables. the.

5.8. Determination Coefficient Test

The coefficient test illustrates that the model in the best research is the ability to explain changes in attitudes towards adopting an induction electric stove, namely 80.8%. This means that success attitude, failure attitude and learning attitude are strong in explaining the attitude of induction cooker adoption.

The ability to explain traits, namely GSG and CYN, is more in two respects. These two things are the attitude of success and the attitude of learning. The smallest ability of the model to explain change is in the failure attitude variable, which is only 6.4%.

Table 5.30 Value of R-squared coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
		0.345	0.064	0.247	0.808	0.395

As the main objective variable, namely the intention to adopt an induction electric stove, only 39.5% could be explained. This means that the attitude of adopting an induction electric stove is less able to explain broadly the intention. This was concluded because 60.5% explained other variables not examined.

5.9. Discussion of Research Results

UseInduction electric stove which is a new technology in developing countries like Indonesia is a problematic behavior due to internal and external factors that hinder behavior in using it. In a developing country like Indonesia, when faced with a choice in the face of a new technology such as an induction electric stove, whether to accept or refuse to use the new technology by considering the failures and successes in its use. (Xie et al., 2008). New technologies such as induction electric stoves because they are still not widely used in society, require a learning process in their use, where this can also be a barrier for the community. (Bagozzi, 1992).

5.9.1. The Effect of Traits (GSC and Cynicism) on Attitude

The influence of traits (GCG and cynicism) on attitude is represented by 6 hypotheses. The representative hypotheses are hypotheses 5 to 10. In general, traits affect attitudes related to the theory of trying. This influence with few exceptions in different directions of influence is generally cynicism and a learning attitude.

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Confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards success. Positive influence means the movement is in the same direction. When self-confidence increases, the attitude of success also increases. Confidence in general has a negative impact on attitudes toward failure. Negative influence means movement in the opposite direction. When general self-confidence increases, attitudes towards failure decrease. Confidence in general has a positive impact on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove. A positive relationship indicates a unidirectional movement. When self-confidence decreases, learning attitudes also decrease, and vice versa.

Cynicism has a negative impact on attitudes towards success. Negative indicates the opposite direction of the two variables. When cynicism increases, the attitude of success decreases. Cynicism has a positive effect on attitudes towards failure. When cynicism increases, attitudes towards failure also increase.

The previous effect description is in agreement with several studies. The presentation of suitability is unified because generally researchers examine all the variables described in different contexts. This research is consistent with research (Chaouali et al., 2017), (Malik et al., 2019), (Barber et al., 2006) and (Chuang et al., 2013).

Cynicism has a positive impact on attitudes toward learning to use an induction hob. This is contrary to research (Chaouali et al., 2017), (Malik et al., 2019), (Barber et al., 2006) and (Chuang et al., 2013). The pattern of influence shows that there are variables that change the direction of influence to be positive. This other side is important for further research.

5.9.2. The Effect of Attitude in Theory of Trying on the Attitude of Adopting an Induction Electric Stove

The research also produced that the attitude variable towards using/adopting an induction electric stove was positively and significantly influenced by the attitude variable towards success and the attitude variable towards learning, but not so towards the attitude towards failure which produced a positive and insignificant result. This is slightly different from the research results of Walid Chaouali and friends (Chaouali et al., 2017), (Malik et al., 2019), (Barber et al., 2006) and (Chuang et al., 2013). The attitude variable towards using/adopting an induction electric stove shows a result of 80.8% which can be explained by the three attitudes, namely attitudes towards success, attitudes towards failure and attitudes towards learning.

The influence of attitude towards the adoption of induction electric stoves is the main influence of the study. This influence study includes three hypotheses, namely hypotheses 1 to 3. The results show that all have a positive effect. But the second hypothesis that has no significant effect is hypothesis two. In addition, the second hypothesis has a different direction from the general view of theory and research.

The two hypotheses are in line with theory and research (Chaouali et al., 2017), (Malik et al., 2019), (Barber et al., 2006) and (Chuang et al., 2013). In general, attitudes towards success have a positive impact on attitudes towards the adoption of induction cookers. If the attitude of success increases, the adoption of induction cookers also increases. Attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove have a positive effect on attitudes towards the adoption of an induction electric stove. The increase in attitudes towards learning increases the attitude towards the adoption of induction electric stoves also increases.

In general, attitudes toward failure have a negative impact on attitudes toward adopting an induction hob (Chaouali et al., 2017), (Malik et al., 2019), (Barber et al., 2006) and (Chuang et al., 2013). This study shows that the effect is not significant and the effect is different, namely positive.

The data pattern indicates the need for attention of other variables for its application. There comes a point where the relationship reverses. From positive to negative, and vice versa.

5.9.3. The Effect of Adoption Attitudes on Adoption Intentions

The research results confirm the conceptual model and the hypothesis that there is a slight difference. Research shows that the variable of intention to use/adopt an induction electric stove is positively and significantly influenced by the variable of attitude towards using/adopting an induction electric stove. This is in line with the research results of Walid Chaouali and friends (Chaouali et al., 2017), (Malik et al., 2019), (Barber et al., 2006) and (Chuang et al., 2013).

This research provides reliable evidence that the multidimensional concept of attitude is compatible with the Theory of Trying. This multidimensional concept of attitude can describe the concept of attitude more completely than other attitude concepts which tend to only have one dimension (Curran & Meuter, 2005), (Jones et al., 2015) and (Kaushik & Rahman, 2015). The concept of a one-dimensional or monolithic attitude, which was previously used as literacy, is considered inappropriate when an attitude is faced with internal and external obstacles (Xie, 2008). The results of the analysis also show that attitudes towards failure have a weaker impact (6.4%) than attitudes towards success (34.5%) and attitudes towards learning (23.5%) on the variable of using/adopting an induction electric stove. This can be justified because the education level of respondents with an undergraduate degree or equivalent is 62% and ages 27 to 44 years are also dominant, so attitudes towards success and attitudes towards learning new technologies such as induction electric stoves are very easy for respondents. With typical respondents who

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are highly educated and relatively young in age, they tend to be able to accept new technologies that are developing in today's society.

5.10. Research Implications

5.10.1. Theoretical Implications

Theoretical implications provide reinforcement to the theory of traits that influence attitudes to the theory of trying. All variables related to traits influence the elements of the theory of trying. However, the influence of cynicism on learning attitudes has a different pattern, namely being positive.

Previous checks proved a new pattern. There is a turning point from the influence from positive to negative, and vice versa. This indicates the need for further study of variables that change the direction of this influence.

Related to the theory of trying itself with one exception is also strengthened. The exception is the effect of failure attitudes on adoption attitudes. The previous check gave a new direction for a turning point from positive to negative influence and vice versa. This shows the need to study variables that change the direction of the effect.

5.10.2. Managerial Implications

The adoption of induction electric stoves by the community requires control or management of traits, namely self-confidence and management of cynicism. Good self-confidence will increase the attitude of success and learning and decrease the attitude of failure. Increased cynicism can decrease success and increase failure. But the other side of cynicism has two patterns. The essence of the pattern is that there is a turning point that needs attention from the symptoms of society. What factors tend to change people's interest despite high cynicism.

The side of the theory of trying provides a downward direction so that the attitude of supporting the adoption of induction electric stoves increases, namely the need for an increase in the attitude of learning and attitude of success. Meanwhile, the attitude of failure can still increase a good attitude towards adoption if it is sensitive to factors that change direction or neutralize the attitude of failure.

5.11. Research Limitations

Researchers convey the limitations of this study, namely:

1. The sample is still too small to represent Indonesia
2. Requires follow-up qualitatively to understand different patterns to discover new knowledge.

CLOSING

6.1. Conclusion

1. Attitude towards success has a significant positive effect on the attitude of induction electric cooker adoption.
2. Attitude towards failure has no negative and insignificant effect on attitude towards induction cooker adoption.
3. Attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove have a significant positive effect on attitudes towards the adoption of an induction electric stove.
4. Attitudes towards the adoption of induction hobs have a positive impact on the intention to adopt induction hobs.
5. Confidence in general has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards success.
6. Confidence in general has a significant negative effect on attitudes towards failure.
7. Confidence in general has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards learning to use an induction electric stove.
8. Cynicism has a significant negative effect on attitudes towards success.
9. Cynicism has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards failure.
10. Cynicism has a significant positive effect on attitudes toward learning to use an induction hob.
11. *Traits* influences the difficulties described by the theory of trying

6.2. Suggestion

1. This research can still be developed by other researchers at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels in Indonesia because there is still a lack of research using the Theory of Trying behavior theory in Indonesia.
2. The adoption of induction cookers requires control over the traits of society, namely general self-confidence and cynicism. But cynicism needs to be carefully controlled because there are two patterns and it really depends on the sensitivity of identifying the factors that influence it. This can be a concern for policy makers such as the government to take strategic steps to popularize induction electric stoves towards Indonesia's Net Zero Emissions (NZE) in 2060 by taking into account the condition of society in terms of general self-confidence and growing cynicism in society. Likewise for induction electric stove manufacturers also need to pay attention to these two factors. Both the Government and induction cooker manufacturers

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can take advantage of social media such as Instagram, Tik Tok, Twitter and other social media to build self-confidence and control public cynicism in providing insights about induction electric stoves so that they can be accepted in society at large. In the present era, you can also take advantage of influencers who can enter broad layers of society so that they can influence or strengthen self-confidence and control people's cynicism in their acceptance of induction electric stoves.

3. The adoption of electric induction cookers for the community requires control of three attitudes from the community. However, attitudes toward failure have two patterns and need to be sensitive to ongoing factor identification. In order to popularize this induction electric stove, the community needs to be invited or brought to these three attitudes so as to form a good experience in the community to have the intention to use an induction electric stove.

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ATTACHMENT

Attachment1

QUESTIONNAIRE

INTENTION TO USE INDUCTION ELECTRIC STOVE ACCORDING TO THEORY OF TRYING

Respondent Data

Gender :	domicile	Age :	Status	Education	Work :	PLN subscription power:
<input type="checkbox"/> Man <input type="checkbox"/> Woman	<input type="checkbox"/> Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam <input type="checkbox"/> North Sumatra <input type="checkbox"/> etc	<input type="checkbox"/> 18 – 26 years <input type="checkbox"/> 27 – 35 years <input type="checkbox"/> 36 – 44 years <input type="checkbox"/> 45 – 53 years <input type="checkbox"/> > 54 years	<input type="checkbox"/> Marry <input type="checkbox"/> Not married	<input type="checkbox"/> SD / equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> Junior High School/equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> SMA / equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> S1/ Equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> S2/ equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> S3/ equivalent <input type="checkbox"/> other	<input type="checkbox"/> students <input type="checkbox"/> ASN/PNS <input type="checkbox"/> private employees <input type="checkbox"/> freelancer <input type="checkbox"/> self-employed <input type="checkbox"/> other	<input type="checkbox"/> 450 VA <input type="checkbox"/> 900VA <input type="checkbox"/> 1300 VA <input type="checkbox"/> 2200 VA <input type="checkbox"/> above 3500 VA

1. Do you know about Induction Electric Stoves? (Yes No)
2. PLN Subscription Power Requirements To try or use a minimum 3500 VA induction electric stove, do you plan to increase the PLN subscription power to a minimum of 3500 VA someday? (Yes No)
3. If you are NOT willing to increase PLN's subscription power, please provide information on the reason?

4. If you are not willing to add to your PLN subscription power of at least 3500 VA, there is no need to continue this questionnaire.

Description of how to fill:

Give a signVfor each of these statements according to the facts that you know or feel in the ASSESSMENT column:

A. General self-confidence

No	STATEMENT	EVALUATION						
(1) Strongly Disagree (4) Undecided (7) Strongly Agree (2) Disagree (5) Somewhat Agree (3) Somewhat Disagree (6) Agree								
1	I feel able to handle myself in most social situations							
2	I am seldom afraid that my actions will cause others to have a low opinion of me							

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3	I am confident to enter a room where others have gathered to strike up a conversation.								
4	In group discussions, I usually feel that my opinion is well received								
5	I make a good first impression on others								
6	When dealing with a group of strangers, my first reaction is always embarrassment								
7	I feel normal when I accidentally go to a formal event with inappropriate clothes								
8	I don't spend a lot of time worrying about what people think of me								
9	When in a group, I am very confident in expressing opinions								
10	I am never at a loss for words when I am introduced to someone								

B. Cynicism

No	STATEMENT	EVALUATION						
<p>(1) Strongly Disagree (4) Undecided (7) Strongly Agree (2) Disagree (5) Somewhat Agree (3) Somewhat Disagree (6) Agree</p>								
1	I think other people will usually lie about the recognition of other people's success							
2	People claim to have ethical standards of honesty/morality, but few adhere to those ethical standards when it comes to money							
3	People only pretend to care more about each other when in reality it's the other way around							
4	It's sad to see selfless people in today's world when so many people are just taking advantage of it							

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5	Most people only stick out for themselves							
6	Most people at heart do not like to put themselves in the shoes of helping others							
7	Most people are dishonest by nature							

C. Attitude towards success

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN		
	(1) Sangat Tidak Menyenangkan (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Menyenangkan (2) Tidak Menyenangkan (5) Agak Menyenangkan (3) Agak Tidak Menyenangkan (6) Menyenangkan			
1	Saya akan mencoba dan bila berhasil menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya			

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN		
	(1) Sangat Tidak Baik (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Baik (2) Tidak Baik (5) Agak Baik (3) Agak Tidak Baik (6) Baik			
2	Saya akan mencoba dan bila berhasil menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya			

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN		
	(1) Sangat Tidak Bahagia (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Bahagia (2) Tidak Bahagia (5) Agak Bahagia (3) Agak Tidak Bahagia (6) Bahagia			
3	Saya akan mencoba dan bila berhasil menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya			

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D. Attitude to failure

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Menyenangkan (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Menyenangkan (2) Tidak Menyenangkan (5) Agak Menyenangkan (3) Agak Tidak Menyenangkan (6) Menyenangkan						
1	Saya akan mencoba dan bila gagal menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Baik (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Baik (2) Tidak Baik (5) Agak Baik (3) Agak Tidak Baik (6) Baik						
2	Saya akan mencoba dan bila gagal menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Bahagia (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Bahagia (2) Tidak Bahagia (5) Agak Bahagia (3) Agak Tidak Bahagia (6) Bahagia						
3	Saya akan mencoba dan bila gagal menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

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E. Attitude towards learning

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Menyenangkan (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Menyenangkan (2) Tidak Menyenangkan (5) Agak Menyenangkan (3) Agak Tidak Menyenangkan (6) Menyenangkan						
1	Belajar untuk menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Baik (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Baik (2) Tidak Baik (5) Agak Baik (3) Agak Tidak Baik (6) Baik						
2	Belajar untuk menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Bahagia (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Bahagia (2) Tidak Bahagia (5) Agak Bahagia (3) Agak Tidak Bahagia (6) Bahagia						
3	Belajar untuk menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

Intention to Use Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying

F. Attitudes towards the adoption of induction electric cookers

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Menyenangkan (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Menyenangkan (2) Tidak Menyenangkan (5) Agak Menyenangkan (3) Agak Tidak Menyenangkan (6) Menyenangkan						
1	Seandainya saya menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Baik (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Baik (2) Tidak Baik (5) Agak Baik (3) Agak Tidak Baik (6) Baik						
2	Seandainya saya menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Bahagia (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Bahagia (2) Tidak Bahagia (5) Agak Bahagia (3) Agak Tidak Bahagia (6) Bahagia						
3	Seandainya saya menggunakan kompor listrik induksi akan membuat perasaan saya						

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G. The intention to adopt an induction electric stove

No	PERNYATAAN	PENILAIAN					
	(1) Sangat Tidak Setuju (4) Ragu-ragu (7) Sangat Setuju (2) Tidak Setuju (5) Agak Setuju (3) Agak Tidak Setuju (6) Setuju						
1	Saya berencana untuk menggunakan kompor listrik induksi di masa depan.						
2	Kemungkinan besar saya akan menggunakan kompor listrik induksi di masa depan.						
3	Saya pikir lebih baik bagi saya untuk menggunakan kompor listrik induksi.						

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Appendix 2 Calculation Results of Phase I

 * Combined loadings and cross-loadings *

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA	Type (a	SE	P value
X1.1	0.583	0.210	0.060	0.032	0.604	-0.613	-0.054	Reflect	0.078	<0.001
X1.2	0.595	-0.104	0.403	0.098	0.215	-0.576	0.095	Reflect	0.078	<0.001
X1.3	0.748	-0.029	-0.004	0.003	0.360	-0.242	-0.027	Reflect	0.075	<0.001
X1.4	0.619	0.204	0.107	-0.247	0.397	-0.667	-0.095	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X1.5	0.789	-0.000	0.044	0.030	-0.063	0.120	-0.002	Reflect	0.074	<0.001
X1.6	0.822	-0.067	-0.172	0.108	-0.102	0.320	-0.061	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X1.7	0.098	0.015	-0.417	0.257	-0.457	0.678	0.089	Reflect	0.088	0.134
X1.8	0.651	0.010	0.010	-0.091	-0.247	0.195	0.139	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X1.9	0.830	-0.104	-0.236	-0.078	-0.276	0.336	0.140	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X1.10	0.862	-0.035	-0.002	0.070	-0.494	0.538	-0.127	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X2.1	0.254	0.641	-0.037	0.097	-0.258	0.336	-0.296	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X2.2	-0.108	0.656	0.572	0.099	-0.256	-0.092	-0.095	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X2.3	-0.119	0.815	-0.129	0.020	-0.131	0.381	0.006	Reflect	0.074	<0.001
X2.4	0.098	0.720	0.181	-0.128	-0.046	-0.120	-0.045	Reflect	0.075	<0.001
X2.5	0.024	0.845	0.117	-0.110	0.141	-0.333	0.103	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X2.6	-0.085	0.812	-0.263	0.034	0.114	0.012	0.201	Reflect	0.074	<0.001
X2.7	-0.024	0.683	-0.383	0.020	0.384	-0.158	0.043	Reflect	0.076	<0.001
Y1.1	-0.014	-0.005	0.981	-0.013	0.052	-0.024	0.047	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y1.2	-0.002	-0.015	0.981	0.053	-0.091	0.065	-0.055	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y1.3	0.017	0.020	0.970	-0.040	0.040	-0.042	0.008	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y2.1	0.021	0.030	-0.064	0.948	-0.052	0.131	0.020	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y2.2	-0.017	0.001	0.043	0.980	-0.082	0.024	0.029	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y2.3	-0.003	-0.031	0.020	0.970	0.133	-0.152	-0.049	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y3.1	-0.004	-0.012	0.051	0.039	0.945	0.034	-0.065	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y3.2	0.026	0.011	-0.000	-0.006	0.970	0.078	0.016	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y3.3	-0.022	0.001	-0.050	-0.032	0.962	-0.112	0.048	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y4.1	-0.034	-0.007	-0.001	0.069	-0.043	0.932	-0.131	Reflect	0.072	<0.001
Y4.2	-0.006	0.012	-0.053	-0.047	0.069	0.959	-0.012	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y4.3	0.040	-0.005	0.054	-0.021	-0.027	0.948	0.141	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y5.1	-0.029	0.008	0.097	-0.009	-0.022	-0.204	0.969	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y5.2	0.002	0.019	0.095	-0.020	0.012	-0.243	0.970	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y5.3	0.031	-0.031	-0.214	0.032	0.011	0.500	0.866	Reflect	0.073	<0.001

Notes: Loadings are unrotated and cross-loadings are oblique-rotated. SEs and P values are for loadings. P values < 0.05 are desirable for reflective indicators.

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Appendix 3 Calculation Results of Phase II

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* Combined loadings and cross-loadings *
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	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA	Type (a	SE	P value
X1.1	0.586	0.210	0.039	0.043	0.560	-0.557	-0.054	Reflect	0.078	<0.001
X1.2	0.596	-0.104	0.399	0.100	0.214	-0.573	0.096	Reflect	0.078	<0.001
X1.3	0.746	-0.030	0.007	-0.003	0.396	-0.286	-0.025	Reflect	0.075	<0.001
X1.4	0.618	0.203	0.114	-0.251	0.425	-0.701	-0.093	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X1.5	0.791	0.000	0.022	0.042	-0.110	0.180	-0.002	Reflect	0.074	<0.001
X1.6	0.823	-0.067	-0.185	0.116	-0.126	0.351	-0.060	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X1.8	0.650	0.010	0.010	-0.091	-0.240	0.187	0.141	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X1.9	0.829	-0.104	-0.243	-0.073	-0.284	0.348	0.141	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X1.10	0.861	-0.035	-0.009	0.074	-0.502	0.550	-0.125	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X2.1	0.249	0.641	-0.029	0.093	-0.234	0.306	-0.295	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X2.2	-0.091	0.656	0.541	0.116	-0.335	0.007	-0.097	Reflect	0.077	<0.001
X2.3	-0.130	0.815	-0.109	0.009	-0.081	0.317	0.007	Reflect	0.074	<0.001
X2.4	0.103	0.720	0.171	-0.122	-0.072	-0.088	-0.045	Reflect	0.075	<0.001
X2.5	0.031	0.845	0.103	-0.102	0.107	-0.290	0.103	Reflect	0.073	<0.001
X2.6	-0.092	0.812	-0.250	0.027	0.143	-0.025	0.201	Reflect	0.074	<0.001
X2.7	-0.030	0.683	-0.372	0.014	0.410	-0.190	0.044	Reflect	0.076	<0.001
Y1.1	-0.015	-0.005	0.981	-0.014	0.055	-0.027	0.047	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y1.2	-0.003	-0.015	0.981	0.052	-0.089	0.063	-0.055	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y1.3	0.018	0.020	0.970	-0.039	0.035	-0.036	0.008	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y2.1	0.017	0.030	-0.057	0.948	-0.032	0.106	0.021	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y2.2	-0.016	0.001	0.041	0.980	-0.086	0.029	0.029	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y2.3	-0.000	-0.030	0.014	0.970	0.118	-0.133	-0.050	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y3.1	-0.003	-0.012	0.049	0.041	0.945	0.042	-0.065	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y3.2	0.025	0.011	0.000	-0.006	0.970	0.077	0.016	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y3.3	-0.023	0.001	-0.048	-0.034	0.962	-0.119	0.048	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y4.1	-0.033	-0.007	-0.002	0.070	-0.046	0.932	-0.131	Reflect	0.072	<0.001
Y4.2	-0.006	0.012	-0.053	-0.047	0.068	0.959	-0.012	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y4.3	0.039	-0.005	0.055	-0.021	-0.024	0.948	0.141	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y5.1	-0.028	0.009	0.095	-0.008	-0.027	-0.197	0.969	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y5.2	0.002	0.019	0.095	-0.020	0.012	-0.243	0.970	Reflect	0.071	<0.001
Y5.3	0.030	-0.031	-0.212	0.031	0.016	0.493	0.866	Reflect	0.073	<0.001

Notes: Loadings are unrotated and cross-loadings are oblique-rotated. SEs and P values are for loadings. P values < 0.05 are desirable for reflective indicators.

Average variances extracted

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
0.532	0.552	0.955	0.934	0.920	0.897	0.877

Intention to Use Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying

Correlations among l.vs. with sq. rts. of AVEs

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
GSC	0.730	-0.054	0.513	-0.098	0.501	0.494	0.352
CYN	-0.054	0.743	-0.044	0.198	-0.009	-0.037	0.033
AS	0.513	-0.044	0.977	-0.203	0.800	0.799	0.611
AF	-0.098	0.198	-0.203	0.966	-0.158	-0.194	0.016
AL	0.501	-0.009	0.800	-0.158	0.959	0.848	0.517
AM	0.494	-0.037	0.799	-0.194	0.848	0.947	0.619
IA	0.352	0.033	0.611	0.016	0.517	0.619	0.936

Note: Square roots of average variances extracted (AVEs) shown on diagonal.

Q-squared coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
		0.345	0.076	0.335	0.808	0.398

Composite reliability coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
0.909	0.895	0.985	0.977	0.972	0.963	0.955

Cronbach's alpha coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
0.886	0.862	0.977	0.965	0.956	0.942	0.928

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 * Indicator weights *

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA	Type (a	SE	P value	VIF	WLS	ES
X1.1	0.122	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.087	0.081	1.852	1	0.072
X1.2	0.124	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.087	0.078	1.642	1	0.074
X1.3	0.156	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.037	1.818	1	0.116
X1.4	0.129	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.087	0.070	1.643	1	0.080
X1.5	0.165	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.029	2.519	1	0.131
X1.6	0.172	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.024	2.729	1	0.141
X1.8	0.136	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.087	0.061	1.819	1	0.088
X1.9	0.173	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.023	3.077	1	0.143
X1.10	0.180	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.019	3.761	1	0.155
X2.1	0.000	0.166	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.028	1.440	1	0.107
X2.2	0.000	0.170	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.026	1.684	1	0.111
X2.3	0.000	0.211	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.085	0.007	2.295	1	0.172
X2.4	0.000	0.186	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.016	1.958	1	0.134
X2.5	0.000	0.219	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.085	0.006	2.738	1	0.185
X2.6	0.000	0.210	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.085	0.008	2.731	1	0.171
X2.7	0.000	0.177	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.086	0.021	2.037	1	0.121
Y1.1	0.000	0.000	0.342	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	12.720	1	0.336
Y1.2	0.000	0.000	0.342	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	12.900	1	0.336
Y1.3	0.000	0.000	0.338	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	7.785	1	0.328
Y2.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.338	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	4.881	1	0.321
Y2.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.350	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	12.899	1	0.343
Y2.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.346	0.000	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	10.399	1	0.336
Y3.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.343	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	4.467	1	0.324
Y3.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.351	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	7.785	1	0.341
Y3.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.349	0.000	0.000	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	6.726	1	0.335
Y4.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.347	0.000	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	3.679	1	0.323
Y4.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.357	0.000	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	5.707	1	0.342
Y4.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.353	0.000	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	4.872	1	0.334
Y5.1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.369	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	25.376	1	0.357
Y5.2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.369	Reflect	0.082	<0.001	25.435	1	0.357
Y5.3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.329	Reflect	0.083	<0.001	2.156	1	0.285

Notes: P values < 0.05 and VIFs < 2.5 are desirable for formative indicators; VIF = indicator variance inflation factor;
 WLS = indicator weight-loading sign (-1 = Simpson's paradox in l.v.); ES = indicator effect size.

Intention to Use Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying

	GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
R-squared			0.345	0.064	0.247	0.808	0.395
Adj. R-squared			0.334	0.048	0.235	0.803	0.390
Composite reliab.	0.909	0.895	0.985	0.977	0.972	0.963	0.955
Cronbach's alpha	0.886	0.862	0.977	0.965	0.956	0.942	0.928
Avg. var. extrac.	0.532	0.552	0.955	0.934	0.920	0.897	0.877
Full collin. VIF	1.413	1.048	3.691	1.133	4.339	4.666	1.842
Q-squared			0.345	0.076	0.335	0.808	0.398
Min	-3.140	-2.334	-4.407	-1.578	-4.488	-1.867	-3.158
Max	1.489	2.464	1.078	2.315	1.099	1.165	0.991
Median	0.163	0.035	0.164	0.257	0.168	0.154	0.100
Mode	1.489	0.065	0.164	0.368	0.168	1.165	0.991
Skewness	-0.307	-0.183	-1.051	0.164	-1.029	-0.460	-0.878
Exc. kurtosis	-0.369	0.088	1.754	-0.384	1.895	-0.812	-0.032
Unimodal-RS	Yes						
Unimodal-KMV	Yes						
Normal-JB	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Normal-RJB	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Histogram	View						

Notes: Unimodal-RS = Rohatgi-Székely test of unimodality; Unimodal-KMV = Klaassen-Mokveld-van Es test of unimodality; Normal-JB = Jarque-Bera test of normality; Normal-RJB = robust Jarque-Bera test of normality; click on "View" cell to see corresponding histogram.

Intention to Use Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying

Model fit and quality indices

Average path coefficient (APC)=0.329, $P<0.001$

Average R-squared (ARS)=0.372, $P<0.001$

Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)=0.362, $P<0.001$

Average block VIF (AVIF)=1.498, acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally ≤ 3.3

Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)=2.591, acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally ≤ 3.3

Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)=0.549, small ≥ 0.1 , medium ≥ 0.25 , large ≥ 0.36

Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)=0.800, acceptable if ≥ 0.7 , ideally = 1

R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)=0.969, acceptable if ≥ 0.9 , ideally = 1

Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)=1.000, acceptable if ≥ 0.7

Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)=0.900, acceptable if ≥ 0.7

Intention to Use Induction Electric Stove According to Theory of Trying

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*****
* Path coefficients and P values *
*****

Path coefficients
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      GSC   CYN   AS    AF    AL    AM    IA

AS    0.528 -0.133
AF    -0.147 0.186
AL    0.517 0.143
AM                0.370 0.034 0.600
IA                                0.628

P values
-----

      GSC   CYN   AS    AF    AL    AM    IA

AS    <0.001 0.064
AF    0.046 0.016
AL    <0.001 0.051
AM                <0.001 0.353 <0.001
IA                                <0.001
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R-squared coefficients

GSC	CYN	AS	AF	AL	AM	IA
		0.345	0.064	0.247	0.808	0.395